

10th

Congress of South East European Society of Perinatal Medicine

SEESPM 2024

The South East European Society
of Perinatal Medicine

25-26
OCTOBER
2024

Hilton Bakırköy Hotel
İstanbul - TÜRKİYE

"with the contribution of The Society
of Maternal Fetal Medicine & Perinatology, Türkiye"

www.seespm2024.org

INVITATION

Dear Colleagues,

It is our pleasure and privilege to invite you to attend the **10th South East European Congress of Perinatal Medicine (SEESPM)** (October 25-26, 2024) and **the 14th Maternal Fetal Medicine and Perinatology Society of Türkiye (TMFTPD)** (October 23-26, 2024) which will be held in İstanbul, Türkiye. The Congress venue is "**Hilton İstanbul Bakırköy**".

The SEESPM is a scientific organization on perinatal Medicine which was founded in 2002. The primary purpose of the Society is to improve the knowledge and skills of physicians practicing in 13 South East European countries and to strengthen their friendships. The congresses of SEESPM are organized every two years with the contributions of the perinatal societies of Albania, Bulgaria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Moldavia, Montenegro, N. Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia and Türkiye.

Perinatology aims to raise healthy generations for societies and protect maternal health. Developments in perinatology, genetics and neonatology have facilitated the follow-up of high-risk pregnancies and ensure the birth of healthier babies.

Perinatal medicine has a major implication not only for the individuals but also for the societies. The philosophy of this societies is not based only to the exchange of expertise between Obstetricians, Neonatologists and any staff dealing with birth, but especially on friendship. Nevertheless, we need to expand our societies, increase cooperation's between the member countries and be able to withdraw our own perinatal results. In this Congress many topics related to this subject will be discussed by experienced lecturers.

İstanbul is the largest city in Türkiye, serving as the country's economic, cultural, and historic hub. The city straddles the Bosphorus Strait, lying in both Europe and Asia, and has a population of over 20 million residents. The history of the city is very old and dates to 3000 years.

The weather will be very nice in October. We believe that the beauties of İstanbul and the level of the Congress will make you happy.

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we look forward to seeing you at the Congress and wish you a pleasant stay in İstanbul.

"We are waiting for you in İstanbul, the meeting point of the world."

The President of SEESPM
Prof. Orion Gliozheni

The President of the Congress
Prof. Dr. Acar Koç

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SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

25 OCTOBER 2024

17.00-17.15 **Welcome of Presidents**
Orion Gliozheni, Acar Koç

Hall A

Session I: "Soranos of Ephesus" Awards
Presidents: *Orion Gliozheni, Acar Koç*

17.15-17.45 **Friendship and Science Awards**
M. Sinan Beksaç

17.45-18.30 **Science Award Lecture**

"Management of PPROM in late preterms."
Diogo Ayres-de-Campos

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

Session II: Keynote Lectures

Chairs: *Orion Gliozheni, Sinan Beksac, Acar Koc*

Hall B

- 08.30-08.50** **Limits of viability**
Milan Stanojevic
- 08.50-09.10** **Use of antenatal corticosteroids**
Enkeleda Prifti
- 09.10-09.30** **Management of preterm labour**
Themistoklis Dagklis
- 09.30-09.50** **The role of bedside lung ultrasound in NICU**
Simona Vladareanu
- 09.50-10.10** **Immunisation in pregnancy**
Ratko Matijevic
- 10.10-10.20** **Discussion**

10.20-10.40 **Coffee Break**

Session VI: Obstetrics Session I

Chairs: *Edvin Vaso, Seval Özgü Erdinç, Snezana Crnogorac*

Hall C

- 08.40-09.00** **Fetal "hypoxia versus distress"; Definition & Identification**
Gökçen Örgül
- 09.00-09.20** **Risk factors for fetal hypoxia: Detection/Surveillance of fetal hypoxia**
Gent Sopa
- 09.20-09.40** **Gestational risk factors for neonatal respiratory morbidity; Preterm&term deliveries**
Iona Rotariou
- 09.40-10.00** **Antenatal corticosteroids**
Atakan Tanacan
- 10.00-10.20** **Intrapartum hypoxia**
Aykut Özek
- 10.20-10.40** **Fetal hypoxia/distress and the value of umbilical cord blood gas analysis in perinatal surveillance/evaluation**
Doruk Cevdi Katlan
- 10.40-10.50** **Discussion**

10:50-11:10 **Coffee Break**

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Session III: Keynote Lectures

Chairs: *Nikolas Papantoniou, Ratko Matijevic, Apostolos Athanasiadis*

Hall B

- 10.40-11.00** **Metabolic infrastructure of pregnant women with TR21 fetuses; Metabolomic analysis**
Sinan Beksaç
- 11.00-11.20** **What is the role of ultrasound in NIPT era?**
Daniel Mureşan
- 11.20-11.40** **Borderline ventriculomegaly**
Atıl Yüksel
- 11.40-12.00** **Key points in the diagnosis and management of fetal neck pathology**
Radu Vladareanu
- 12.00-12.20** **A woman's microbiome and obstetrics and perinatal risks: What do they have in common?**
Volodymyr V. Artyomenko
- 12.20-12.30** **Discussion**

Session VII: Obstetrics Session II

Chairs: *Simona Vladareanu, Filiz Yanık, Gökhan Yıldırım*

Hall C

- 11.30-11.50** **Evidence-based approaches to managing vaginal infections during pregnancy**
Koray Görkem Saçınıtı
- 11.50-12.10** **Progesterone use in pregnancy**
Mert Turgal
- 12.10-12.30** **Antihypertensive use in pregnancy**
Erkan Çağlayan
- 12.30-12.50** **Prediction of preterm birth**
Elko Gliozheni
- 12.50-13.00** **Discussion**

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

11:30 - 13:00

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-1

Chairs: **Edvin Vaso, Cenk Sayın, Oya Demirci**

Hall D

- OP-01 A case of TARP syndrome meeting all acronym criteria
Ceren Sağlam, Ibrahim Ömeroğlu, Atalay Ekin
- OP-57 Does foramen ovale restriction matter in the intrauterine period?
Sevim Tuncer Can, **Ceren Sağlam**, Bahar Konuralp Atakul
- OP-02 Fetal Enterolithiasis: A Pivotal Sonographic Marker for Early Diagnosis of Urorectal Septum Malformation Sequence
Reşat Mısırlıoğlu, Aydın Öcal, Ali Cetin, Fatma Nihal Öztürk
- OP-03 The Importance of Whole Exome Sequencing in Prenatal Diagnosis of Vermian Pathologies: A Case Report
Reşat Mısırlıoğlu, Çağseli Göksu Özgün Selçuk, Filiz Yarsilikal Guleroglu
- OP-04 The Role of the Glasgow Prognostic Score in Predicting Outcomes in Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes
Gülşan Karabay, **Merve Ayas Ozkan**, Gülşah Dağdeviren
- OP-05 Perinatal outcome of pregnancies complicated by immune thrombocytopenic purpura: a tertiary referral-center experience
Zeynep Şeyhanlı, Ahmet Şeyhanlı, Şevki Çelen
- OP-06 The Comparative Effects of High-Dose and Low-Dose Oxytocin Protocols on Cervical Dilatation During Labor
Edip Alptug Kir, Bilal Emre Erzeneoglu, Fatma Caner Cabukoglu, Ozgur Deren
- OP-07 Cases in which selective fetal reduction: Microwave Ablation was performed in our clinic, indications, pregnancy outcomes
Aslıhan Kurt, Selcan Sinacı, Didem Yücel Yetişkin
- OP-08 Celox use in late postpartum hemorrhage
Gunel Eliyeva, **Recep Taha Ağaoğlu**, Sevki Celen
- OP-09 A case with Schinzel-Giedion syndrome
Ozlem Aldemir Bukagikiran, Oya Demirci
- OP-10 Management of isolated fetal pleural effusion cases
Gülten Çirkin Tekeş
- OP-11 Ultrasonographic findings and clinical management of short rib thoracic dysplasia 18 with polydactyly: case report
Kubilay Çanga, Şevki Çelen
- OP-12 Multidisciplinary Management of a High-Risk Pregnancy with Osler-Weber-Rendu Syndrome (Hereditary Hemorrhagic Telangiectasia), Behçet's Disease and Common Variable Immunodeficiency (CVID)
Ruken Dayanan

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

11:30 - 13:00

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-1

Chairs: **Edvin Vaso, Cenk Sayın, Oya Demirci**

Hall D

- OP-13 A Rare case report diagnosis at 16th week: FATCO
Elif Ayan Avcı, And Yavuz, Hasan Berkan Sayal, Gul Alkan Bulbul, Büşra Tsakır,
Gökalp Kabacaoğlu
- OP-14 Giant Fetal Neck Mass Case Report with Ex Utero Intrapartum Treatment (EXIT) Procedure
Cem Dagdelen, Osman Ince, Tuğçe Tunç Acar, Inanc Mendilcioglu
- OP-15 A rare anomaly: Tricuspid atresia-VSD, double outlet left ventricle and situs
inversus totalis
Abdullah Tabakçı, Mucize Eric Ozdemir
- OP-16 Emergency Rescue Cervical Cerclage With Bulging Membranes: Evaluation Of
Four Cases In The Light Of The Literature
Elif Betül Esmer, Mustafa Ayhan Ekici
- OP-17 A Rare Condition Identified by Prenatal Diagnosis: Fetal Adrenal Hemorrhage
Büşra Tsakır, And Yavuz, Gul Alkan Bulbul, Hasan Berkan Sayal
- OP-18 Mulibrey nanism, a rare cause of non immune hydrops fetalis
Coşkun Ümit, Canan Tapkan, Ozkan Hayit, Elif Akkaş Yilmaz, Zehra Vural Yilmaz,
Gülsüm Kayhan
- OP-19 Prenatally Diagnosed Neuroblastoma- A Case Report
Esra Nuhoglu Bilgin, Pınar Tokdemir Çalış, Hatice Aydın Salman, Arzu Sümer Ortaç,
Esin Şahin Toruk, Deniz Karçaaltıncaba

13.00- 14.00

LUNCH

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

12.45-14.00 General Assembly of SEESPM (Lunch)

Session IV: Keynote Lectures

Chairs: *Aris Antsaklis, Diogo Ayres-de-Campos, Daniel Mureşan*

Hall B

14.00-14.20 **Laser in Obstetrics**
Nikolas Papantoniou

14.20-14.40 **Ultrasound in labor**
Edvin Vaso

14.40-15.00 **Methods to safely reduce C/S rates**
Apostolos Athanasiadis

15.00-15.20 **Placenta percreta: A new epidemic**
George Daskalakis

15.20-15.40 **Treatment of complications in monochorionic twin pregnancies**
Vesna Mandic-Markovic

15.40-15.50 **Discussion**

Session VIII: Fetal Medicine Session

Chairs: *Enkeleida Prifti, Şevki Çelen, Esra Esim Büyükbayrak*

Hall C

14.00-14.20 **Left ventricle outflow tract abnormalities**
Nihal Şahin Uysal

14.20-14.40 **Mild ventriculomegaly diagnosis and management**
Pınar Çalış

14.40-15.00 **Fetal cystic renal disease**
Özgür Kara

15.00-15.20 **Fetal intestinal obstruction**
Murat Çağan

15:20-15.30 **Diafragmatic hernia: Diagnosis and outcome**
Gülşah Aynaoglu Yıldız

15.30-15.40 **Discussion**

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

14:00 - 15:30

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-2

Chairs: **Volodymyr V. Artyomenko, Filiz Yanık, Derya Eroğlu**

Hall D

- OP-21 Ultrasonographic Findings And Clinical Management Of A Case Of Thoracophagus in Monochorionic Multiple Pregnancy: Case Report
Aziz Kindan, Can Ozan Ulusoy
- OP-22 Congenital Sodium Diarrhea: A Case Report
Tuğçe Tunç Acar, Osman Ince, Cem Dagdelen, Inanç Mendilcioğlu
- OP-23 Peroperative uterine packing with chitosan-covered tamponade to treat placental bed bleeding in a case of placenta previa
Doruk Cevdi Katlan, Nebahat Uzunay
- OP-24 Differential diagnosis of seizure in a hypertensive pregnant women: a case report
Abdullah Acar, Emine Akkuş, **Havva Güleli**, Canan Ünal
- OP-25 A rare diagnosis in pregnancy: chronic aortic dissection
Gizem Kul, Munip Akalin, Koray Ak, Fatih Ozturk, Esra Esim Buyukbayrak
- OP-26 From physiological umbilical hernia to Beckwith-Wiedemann Syndrome
Seval Yılmaz Ergani, Harun Egemen Tolunay
- OP-27 inv(5)(q15q33) in both parents associated with recurrent pregnancy loss
Ekin Kuntsal, İlknur Suer, Murat Kaya, Tugba Kalayci, Şükrü Öztürk, Kivanç Çefle
- OP-28 Case Presentations of Urorectal Septum Malformation
Esin Şahin Toruk, Pınar Çalış, Hatice Aydın Salman, Arzu Ortaç, Esra Nuhoğlu Bilgin, Deniz Karçaaltıncaba
- OP-29 Right Atrial Isomerism, A Rare Case Report
Yasin Altekin, Nizamettin Bozbay, Gokcen Orgul
- OP-30 A Rare Heart Anomaly: Familial Non-Compaction Cardiomyopathy
Abdullah Tabakci, Mucize Eric Ozdemir
- OP-31 Prenatal diagnosis of Beckwith-Wiedemann Syndrome
Hale Ankara Aktaş, İlayda Gercik Arzık, **Raziye Torun**, Hakan Golbasi
- OP-32 A Case Report of Semilobar Holoprosencephaly with Malalignment Ventricular Septal Defect and Narrow Cisterna Magna
Meltem Caliskan, Fulya Sultan Karaduman, Ali Cetin, Numan Cim, Filiz Yarsilikal Guleroglu
- OP-33 Thanatophoric Dysplasia Type 1: A Case Report
Fulya Sultan Karaduman, Meltem Çalışkan
- OP-34 Twin pregnancy complicated with Listeria monocytogenes infection: a rare case report
Zeynep Nur Kömürcü, Bilge Kapudere, Sevil Eraslan Cicek, Reyhan Ayaz
- OP-35 Recurrent cerebellar hypoplasia; Genetic testing is not always useful
Nizamettin Bozbay, **Yasin Altekin**, Gokcen Orgul

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

14:00 - 15:30

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-2

Chairs: **Volodymyr V. Artyomenko, Filiz Yanık, Derya Eroğlu**

Hall D

OP-36

Fetal mediastinal teratoma resulting in hydrops
Raziye Torun, Sevim Tuncer Can, Atalay Ekin

OP-37

Mosaic Trisomy 20 and Corrected Transposition of the Great Artery: Case Report
Arzu Sümer Ortaç, Pınar Çalış, Hatice Aydın Salman, Esra Nuhoğlu Bilgin,
Esin Şahin Toruk, Ayşe Berin Acar, Şüheda Günbay, Tuncay Nas, Deniz Karçaaltıncaba

OP-38

Heterotopic tubal pregnancy with intrauterine twin implantation after clomiphene citrate
Simge Berrak Beyoğlu Oruc

OP-39

Mechanical Valve Thrombosis in a Pregnant Women: A Case Report
Hatice Aydın Salman, Pınar Tokdemir Çalış, Arzu Sümer Ortaç, Esra Nuhoğlu Bilgin,
Esin Şahin Toruk, Mehmet Zeki Taner, Deniz Karçaaltıncaba

OP-40

Surgical Resection of Obstructed Part of Robert's Uterus During Cesarean Section
Savas Gundogan, **Ece Akgor**

15.30-16.00

Coffee Break

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

Session V: Keynote Lecture

Chairs: *George Daskalakis, Radu Vladareanu, Vesna Mandic-Markovic*

Hall B

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 16.20-16.40 | The importance of ultrasound in detecting monogenic diseases
<i>Snezana Crnogorac</i> |
| 16.40-17.00 | Obesity epidemic and reproduction
<i>Aris Antsaklis</i> |
| 17.00-17.20 | Recurrent pregnancy loss:What is the evidence base?
<i>Orion Gliozheni</i> |
| 17.20-17.40 | Celox experience in Romania
<i>Edvin Vaso</i> |
| 17.40-18.00 | An uncommon instance of tubal pregnancy with a vital fetus at the 13th week of gestation
<i>Vlora Ademi Ibishi</i> |
| 18.00-18.10 | Discussion |

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

16:00 - 18:00

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-3

Chairs: *Daniel Mureşan, Apostolos Athanasiadis,
Tamer Mungan, Milan Stanojevic*

Hall C

- OP-41 Identifying The Risk Factors And The Outcomes Of Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS): Data From A University Hospital Setting In Tirana, Albania
Enkeleda Prifti, Enxhi Vrapı, Lorela Hysi
- OP-42 Antenatal corticosteroids: a thoughtful and considered action!
Enkeleda Prifti
- OP-43 Endothelial dysfunction, arterial stiffness, retinal microvasculature changes in high-risk preeclampsia women: Impact of smoking
Kaltrina Kutllovci Hasani, Mila Cervar Zivkovic, Ursula Hiden, Adam Salon, Manurishi Nanda, Bianca Steuber, Katharina Eberhard, Christina Stern, Karoline Mayer Pickel, Nandu Goswami
- OP-44 A case of colostomia bipolaris after a perineal rüptüre
Ilma Dadić, Adnan Pezo, Aida Đurđević, Asim Spahović, Emina Ahmetlić
- OP-45 Combination of longitudinal parallel compression suture and intra uterine balloon catheter: a promising technique to prevent postpartum hemorrhage in placenta accreta spectrum
I Made Ngurah Surya Adi Witama, Yuditiya Purwosunu, Amanda Rumondang
- OP-46 Central Nervous System Anomalies In Perinatal Autopsies
Nuran Tutar, Zuhul Akçören
- OP-47 Retrospective Analysis of Characteristics and Neonatal Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Intrauterine Fetal Blood Transfusion
Recep Taha Ağaoğlu, Şevki Çelen
- OP-48 Pregnancy during and after cancer treatment: experience of a single tertiary center
Gizem Kul, Esra Esim Buyukbayrak
- OP-49 Comparison of Malformation Rates in Fetuses of Pregnant Women with Gestational Diabetes and Pregestational Diabetes: A Retrospective Cohort Study
Alper Sayir, Derya Sahin Basdelioglu, Hatice Akkaya, Ayse Seval Ozgu Erdinc
- OP-50 Maternal Outcomes of Pregnancy Terminations in Women with a History of Uterine Surgery: A Retrospective Analysis
Nazan Vanlı Tonyalı, Betül Tokgöz
- OP-51 Giant cystic hygroma and EXIT procedure, case report
Seval Yılmaz Ergani

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

26 OCTOBER 2024

16:00 - 18:00

ORAL PRESENTATIONS-3

Chairs: *Daniel Mureşan, Apostolos Athanasiadis,
Tamer Mungan, Milan Stanojevic*

Hall C

- OP-52 Follow up of pregnant women with sleep disorders in the first trimester in terms of adverse obstetric outcomes: A prospective cohort study
Denizhan Demir, Ayse Seval Ozgu Erdinc
- OP-53 Perinatal Outcomes in Pregnant Women Exposed to the February 2023 Earthquake: A Retrospective Analysis from Osmaniye
Erdal Şeker, Hatun Çolak
- OP-54 Distribution of Limb Anomalies Diagnosed in Prenatal Screening and Pregnancy Outcomes - Tertiary Centre Experience
Betül Kurgun, Ahmet Kurt, Yüksel Oğuz
- OP-55 Outcomes of pregnant women and fetuses followed up with suspicion of sacrococcygeal teratoma
Abdullah Tabakçı, **Mucize Eric Ozdemir**
- OP-56 Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes in Triplet Pregnancies: A Retrospective Analysis
Özgür Volkan Akbulut, Gizem Aktemur, Ali Turhan Çağlar
- OP-58 Postpartum Hemolytic Uremic Syndrome
Özge Öztürk, Ali Turhan Çağlar
- OP-59 Limb Body Wall Complex: A Case Series of a Rare Anomaly
Ahmet Arif Filiz, Şevki Çelen
- OP-60 Post-laser Twin Anemia Polycythemia Sequence: A Case Report
Tuğçe Tunç Acar, Osman Ince, Cem Dağdelen, İnanç Mendilcioğlu
- OP-61 Comparison of birth outcomes of pregnant women with lateral placenta with other locations of placenta: A prospective cohort study
Durmus Tekemen, Ayse Seval Ozgu-Erdinc
- OP-62 Awareness and attitudes of pregnant women about prenatal screening and diagnostic tests
Didem Kaymak, Tuğba Kalaycı, Gözde Yeşil Sayın, Birsen Karaman, Seher Başaran, Ceren Çebi, Betül Tümbaş, Rıza Madazlı
- OP-63 Association Between Umbilical Cord Blood Gas Values And Mode Of Delivery In Cases Of Preeclampsia
Mehmet Alican Sapmaz, Murat Polat, Sait Erbey, **Aziz Kından**
- OP-64 Budd Chiari syndrome presenting with abdominal wall varices in pregnancy: a case report
İlayda Gercik Arzık, Hale Ankara Aktaş, **Didem Gül Sarıtaş**, Atalay Ekin

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

OP-01

A case of TARP syndrome meeting all acronym criteria

Ceren Sağlam, İbrahim Ömeroğlu, Atalay Ekin

Division of Perinatology, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Izmir City Hospital, Izmir, Türkiye

OBJECTIVE: It's aimed to emphasize the importance of second-trimester sonography for detecting severe genetic anomalies.

MATERIAL-METHOD: The patient referred to our center was examined by ultrasonography.

RESULTS: A 33-year-old, G1P0, 21w5d pregnant had fetal biometry compatible with 19-20 weeks (3 percentile) in the ultrasound. In the neurosonography, tegmentovermian angle was 36 degrees and the appearance was compatible with Blake pouch cyst. Retrognathia and isolated cleft palate were detected. In 3D sonography, the philtrum was seen to be longer than normal. A single atrium structure secondary to a large atrial septal defect (ASD) was observed in the fetal echocardiography. In the 3-vessel-trachea section, superior vena cava (SVC) couldn't be visualised on the right. Persistent left SVC (PLSVC) and a hypoplastic thymus was observed. In addition, talipes equinovarus in the left foot, horseshoe kidney, and a single umbilical artery were noted. Although the fetal karyotype and microarray results of amniocentesis were normal, a hemizygous c.2377c>T mutation was observed in the 21st exon of the RBM10 gene as a result of whole exome sequencing (WES). This mutation is interpreted as pathogenic which is inherited X-linked TARP syndrome. The family, who was offered the option of pregnancy termination, terminated the pregnancy.

CONCLUSION: TARP syndrome is caused by hemizygous mutation in the RBM10 gene on chromosome Xp11. However it's an acronym (talipes equinovarus, ASD, Robin sequence (micrognathia, cleft palate, glossoptosis), and PLSVC), most patients don't meet all these criteria but some additional anomalies like central nervous system dysfunction, renal abnormalities, variable cardiac and distal limb anomalies. It's rare and mostly lethal in antenatal or early postnatal period.

Keywords: TARP syndrome, RBM10 gene, prenatal sonography

Figure 1

There are images of the detected anomalies (a, tegmentovermian degree of 36; b, Blake pouch cyst; c, long philtrum (arrow) and micro-retrognathia (dotted arrow); d, 3D visualization of fetal face and philtrum; e, single atria secondary to ASD; f, hypoplastic thymus; g, talipes equinovarus of the left foot; h, single umbilical artery at the section of perivesical area) of the fetus diagnosed as TARP syndrome.

OP-02

Fetal Enterolithiasis: A Pivotal Sonographic Marker for Early Diagnosis of Urorectal Septum Malformation Sequence

Reşat Mısırlıoğlu¹, Aydın Öcal¹, Ali Cetin¹, Fatma Nihal Öztürk²

¹Department of Perinatology, Haseki Research and Training Hospital, İstanbul, Turkey

²Department of Genetics, Haseki Research and Training Hospital, İstanbul, Turkey

INTRODUCTION: Urorectal septum malformation sequence (URSMS) is a rare congenital anomaly characterized by incomplete partition of the cloaca. Early prenatal diagnosis remains challenging due to variable presentation and low incidence. This case report highlights the significance of fetal enterolithiasis as a key ultrasound finding in diagnosing URSMS. **Case Presentation:** A 27-year-old G2P1 woman was referred at 18 weeks' gestation for suspected fetal anomalies. Detailed ultrasound revealed multiple abnormalities including Fallot's tetralogy, cleft lip and palate, renal anomalies, and critically, bowel dilation with enterolithiasis. Chromosomal analysis showed 46,--,r(18)(p11.2q23). The combination of findings led to a prenatal diagnosis of URSMS. **DISCUSSION:** Enterolithiasis, while infrequently reported, emerged as a crucial diagnostic marker in this case. Recent literature suggests its high specificity for bowel obstruction in URSMS. The ring chromosome 18 finding emphasizes the importance of comprehensive genetic evaluation in complex fetal anomalies. Early diagnosis allowed for timely counseling and management planning. **CONCLUSION:** This case underscores the value of meticulous prenatal ultrasound and the specific significance of fetal enterolithiasis in early URSMS diagnosis. It highlights the need for heightened awareness of this rare condition among perinatologists to ensure optimal management and outcomes.

Keywords: : Urorectal septum malformation sequence, enterolithiasis, prenatal diagnosis

OP-03

The Importance of Whole Exome Sequencing in Prenatal Diagnosis of Vermian Pathologies: A Case Report

Reşat Mısırlıoğlu, Çağseli Göksu Özgün Selçuk, Filiz Yarsilikal Guleroglu

Department of Perinatology, Haseki Research and Training Hospital, İstanbul, Turkey

INTRODUCTION: Prenatal diagnosis of fetal central nervous system anomalies remains challenging, particularly in cases involving vermian pathologies. This case report highlights the critical role of Whole Exome Sequencing (WES) in accurately diagnosing a complex fetal presentation initially suspected as vermian aplasia. **CASE:** A 28-year-old primigravida was referred to our perinatal clinic at 21 weeks of gestation due to suspected vermian aplasia, micrognathia, retrognathia, and postaxial polydactyly in both hands detected during a routine anomaly scan. Our detailed neurosonography revealed additional findings suggestive of molar tooth sign, tulip sign, and possible micropenis. Fetal MRI at 23 weeks and 4 days, however, did not confirm the cranial anomalies or molar tooth sign, only noting retrognathia. WES was performed, revealing a point variant and a heterozygous deletion in exon 1 of the MKS1 gene. **DISCUSSION:** This case underscores the importance of integrating advanced genetic testing, particularly WES, with conventional imaging techniques in prenatal diagnosis. The discrepancies between ultrasound and MRI findings, coupled with the genetic results, demonstrate the complexity of diagnosing fetal central nervous system anomalies and the value of a multidisciplinary approach. **CONCLUSION:** This report emphasizes the crucial role of WES in providing accurate diagnoses, enabling appropriate genetic counseling, and informing pregnancy management decisions in cases of suspected fetal anomalies.

Keywords: Whole Exome Sequencing, vermian aplasia, prenatal diagnosis

Genital anomaly

'tulip sign?', micropenis?

Postaxial polydactyly of hand

Sagittal image of posterior fossa

Vermian aplasia and retrognathic mandible

The Molar Tooth (MTS) Sign

An abnormally deep interpeduncular fossa; elongated thick, and maloriented superior cerebellar peduncles; and absent or hypoplastic cerebellar vermis that together give the appearance of a 'molar tooth' sign.

OP-04

The Role of the Glasgow Prognostic Score in Predicting Outcomes in Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes

Gülşan Karabay, Merve Ayas Ozkan, Gülşah Dağdeviren

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INTRODUCTION: This study aims to evaluate the utility of Glasgow Prognostic Score (GPS) in predicting maternal and fetal inflammation and perinatal outcomes in Preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM) patients.

METHODS: This retrospective study included 110 PPRM patients between 24 and 34 weeks of gestation admitted to the Perinatology Clinic of Ankara Etlik City Hospital from January 2023 to January 2024. GPS was calculated from C-reaktif protein (CRP) and albumin levels, classifying patients into three groups: Score 0 (CRP <10 mg/L and albumin \geq 35 g/L), Score 1 (CRP \geq 10 mg/L or albumin <35 g/L), and Score 2 (CRP \geq 10 mg/L and albumin <35 g/L). Maternal age, gestational age at hospitalization, hospitalization-birth interval, gestational age at delivery, neonatal Apgar scores, neonatal CRP levels, and umbilical cord arterial pH were compared.

RESULTS: No statistically significant differences were observed between GPS groups in terms of maternal age, gestational age at hospitalization, hospitalization-birth interval, gestational age at delivery, APGAR score at 1st minute, APGAR score at 5th minute, neonatal CRP levels and umbilical cord arterial Ph ($p = 0.688$, $p = 0.436$, $p = 0.573$, $p = 0.176$, $p = 0.275$, $p = 0.137$, $p = 0.876$, $p = 0.334$, respectively).

CONCLUSION: Although the Glasgow Prognostic Score may offer a non-invasive approach for assessing inflammation in PPRM, its predictive value for adverse neonatal outcomes remains inconclusive. Further studies with larger populations are needed to clarify its role in clinical practice for managing PPRM.

Keywords: Adverse Neonatal Outcomes; Glasgow Prognostic Score; Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes

Maternal characteristics and perinatal outcomes of the participants

	Score 0 N:44	Score 1 N:34	Score 2 N:32	P value
Maternal age (year)	27 (11)	27 (13)	27 (10)	0,688
Gestational age at hospitalization (week)	30,5 (3,9)	29,4 (6,5)	30,6 (4,4)	0,436
Hospitalization-birth interval (day)	4 (15)	2 (6)	2 (6)	0,573
Gestational age at delivery (week)	32 (3,2)	31,1 (6,2)	31,6 (4,9)	0,176
APGAR score at 1st minute	7 (2)	6 (3)	7 (1)	0,275
APGAR score at 5th minute	9 (1)	8 (2)	8 (1)	0,137
Neonatal CRP (mg/L)	0,21 (1,45)	0,27 (0,91)	0,23 (0,88)	0,876
Umbilical cord arterial pH	7,29 (0,13)	7,3 (0,14)	7,3 (0,12)	0,334

OP-05

Perinatal outcome of pregnancies complicated by immune thrombocytopenic purpura: a tertiary referral-center experience

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OBJECTIVE: We aimed to evaluate the perinatal outcomes in pregnant women with idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP) in our perinatology department.

METHODS: A retrospective analysis of 34 pregnancies diagnosed with ITP was conducted between 2022 and 2023 at a tertiary centers where a total of 12456 births occurred. Demographic, clinical and laboratory characteristics, complications, treatment methods, and perinatal outcomes were examined.

RESULTS: The median maternal age was 29, and their ages ranged from 20 to 41. Cesarean delivery was performed in 58.06% of the pregnancies. The median gestational age at delivery was 38.4 weeks, and the mean birth weight was 2944.7±699.35 grams. The history of splenectomy was noted in 12.9%. Preterm delivery occurred in 25.8% of the cases, with 16.12% presenting intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and 16.12% requiring neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission. The median maternal platelet counts during the delivery were 100/μL (3-227). The median platelet count of newborns is 284/μL(55-475). In one newborn (3.22%), neonatal alloimmune thrombocytopenia (NAIT) was detected. The most common (16.12 %) ITP treatment method is the combination of steroids, IVIG and platelet transfusion. Postpartum hemorrhage was observed in 12.9% of cases.

CONCLUSIONS: Pregnancy complicated by ITP is associated with various maternal and fetal complications. The management of these pregnancies requires a multidisciplinary team consisting of a maternal fetal medicine specialist, hematologist, anesthesiologist and neonatologist.

Keywords: immune thrombocytopenia, ITP, perinatal outcome

Table 1. Demographic, clinical characteristics of pregnancies with ITP

	Mean±SD	Median (min-max)	Number (n), Percent (%)
Maternal age (year)	28.3±5.5	29 (20-41)	-
Gravidity	2.19 ±1.4	2 (1-6)	-
Parity			
Nulliparous	-	-	6 (19.3%)
Multiparous	-	-	25 (80.6%)
History of abortus	0.38±0.88	0 (0-4)	-
BMI	28.71 ±3.7	28.7 (22.2 –36.4)	-
Smoking	-	-	1 (3.22%)
Splenectomy	-	-	4 (12.9%)
Miscarriage	-	-	3 (8.82%)
Caesarean delivery	-	-	18 (58.06%)
Gestational age at delivery	37.9± 2.21	38.4 (31.4-41.1)	-
Birth-weight (g)	2944.7±699.35	2955(1380-4200)	-
Apgar score at 1 min <7	8.16±1.69	9 (0-9)	-
Apgar score at 5 min <7	9.16±1.82	10 (0-10)	-

Abbreviations: BMI: body mass index

Table 2. Maternal complications, perinatal outcomes, treatment methods and laboratory datas of pregnancies with ITP

	Mean±SD	Median (min-max)	Number (n), Percent (%)
Hypertensive disorders	-	-	1 (3.22%)
Gestational diabetes mellitus	-	-	1 (3.22%)
Preterm delivery	-	-	8 (25.8%)
IUGR	-	-	5 (16,12%)
Intrauterine foetal demise	-	-	1 (3.22%)
Neonatal Alloimmune Trombocytopenia (NAIT)	-	-	1 (3.22%)
Postpartum hemorrhage	-	-	4 (12.9%)
NICU	-	-	5 (16,12%)
Maternal platelet count at delivery (×109/l)	110,74±71	100 (3-227)	-
Fetal platelet count (×109/l)	284,96±87,09	284 (55-475)	-
Treatment during pregnancy, at delivery			
No medication	-	-	18 (58.1%)
Steroids	-	-	4 (12.9%)
Steroids + IVIG	-	-	2 (6.45 %)
Steroids + Platelet transfusion	-	-	2 (6.45%)
Steroids + IVIG + Platelet transfusion	-	-	5 (16.12%)

Abbreviations: IVIG: intravenous immunoglobulin IUGR: Intrauterine Growth Restriction NICU: neonatal intensive care unit

OP-06

The Comparative Effects of High-Dose and Low-Dose Oxytocin Protocols on Cervical Dilatation During Labor

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Childbirth consists of three stages. Stage 1 involves cervical dilation, ending with full dilation. Stage 2 covers the period from full dilation to birth, and Stage 3 from birth to placenta expulsion. Stage 1 includes the latent phase (0–6 cm) and the active phase (6 cm to full dilation).

Oxytocin (Synpitan) is commonly used to accelerate labor, with two protocols: high-dose (4–10 mU/min) and low-dose (1–4 mU/min).

Methodology

This retrospective study analyzed deliveries at Hacettepe University Hospital between January 2018 and May 2024. Patients who had amniotomy at 6 cm dilation and started oxytocin at the same point were included. Patients with spontaneous rupture or who received other medications were excluded. Time intervals between 6 cm to 10 cm, 10 cm to birth, and 6 cm to birth were compared using the Mann-Whitney test for both primigravids and multigravids. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS: Out of 1000 patients, 121 primigravid and 131 multigravid participants were analyzed. Among primigravids, 43 received high-dose and 73 received low-dose oxytocin. Among multigravids, 67 received high-dose and 64 received low-dose. No statistically significant differences were found between high-dose and low-dose groups for any of the time intervals in either primigravid or multigravid groups.

Discussion

The study found no significant difference between high-dose and low-dose oxytocin protocols. Given the higher risk of complications with high-dose oxytocin, low-dose oxytocin is recommended. Larger studies are needed to confirm these findings.

Keywords: High Dose Oxytocin, Low Dose Oxytocin, Cervical Dilatation

OP-07

Cases in which selective fetal reduction: Microwave Ablation was performed in our clinic, indications, pregnancy outcomes

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CASE 1: 24 years old, gravida(G)1. IVF pregnancy. Monochorionic diamniotic (MCDA) twin pregnancy was referred at 17th week due to cystic hygroma in one fetus. We were observed generalized edema and cystic hygroma in one fetus (Figure 1). Microwave ablation (MWA) procedure was performed 2 minute 40 watt. Under continuous ultrasound guidance, MWA antenna was inserted percutaneously into the abdominal cavity of the target fetus, with the tip positioned in the abdomen near the cord insertion. The heartbeat stopped after the procedure. Pregnancy gave birth by cesarean delivery at 35th week due to oligohydramnios and severe preeclampsia. A healthy baby was born with 8-9 apgar score and 3120 gr.

CASE 2: 22 years old, G1. Monochorionic triamniotic spontaneous triplet pregnancy. The pregnancy was referred at 16th week due to fetal anomaly in one fetus. The fetus in the middle was dead. The fetus on the right had a cystic hygroma. We observed normal fetal anatomy the fetus on the left. Currently in the 24th week of pregnancy.

CASE 3: 24 years old, G1. MCDA twin pregnancy was referred at 15th week due to fetal anomaly in one fetus. Severe ventriculomegaly was detected in one fetus. TORCH negative. We were evaluated oligohydramnios and stuck twin. Currently in the 27th week of pregnancy.

CASE 4: 24 years old, G2. MCDA twin pregnancy at 22th week. The pregnancy applied for detailed fetal anatomic ultrasound examination. Her husband was also her cousin. We were observed lumbosacral 3*2cm. meningomyelocele (Figure 2), ventriculomegaly, lemon sign, cerebellar herniation in one fetus. Currently in the 28th week of pregnancy. All amniocentesis results were normal. All cases have been informed about the risks. Currently there aren't any obstetric problem in the cases.

Keywords: ablation, microwave, case

figure 1

figure 2

OP-08

Celox use in late postpartum hemorrhage

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BACKGROUND:

Late postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is significant vaginal bleeding occurring between 24 hours and 6 weeks post-delivery, with an incidence of 0.2%-0.8%. Causes include placental retention, endometritis, subinvolution of the placental bed, and coagulopathies. Effective treatments are crucial for cases unresponsive to uterotonic medications and balloon tamponade.

Case Presentation:

A 32-year-old G1P1 patient, treated with a Foley catheter and Bakri balloon for late PPH on day 12 post-cesarean, was referred to our center for bleeding. At the initial evaluation hemoglobin was 7.7 g/dL, platelet count was 83,000, fibrinogen was 221 and active vaginal bleeding despite a properly placed Bakri balloon. At the first ultrasound examination, the balloon was seen in the uterine cavity and although it was in place, the bleeding continued. After appropriate transfusion was administered, the Bakri balloon was deflated in the operating room and therapeutic curettage was performed. But the bleeding persisted, preparations were made for a laparotomy, but given the patient's age and her desire for fertility, CELOX gauze was placed in the uterine cavity. Postoperatively, the patient was monitored closely, with no hematoma or bleeding seen on ultrasound. The gauze was removed after 12 hours, and the patient discharged with recovery.

CONCLUSION: Late PPH is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality. Laparotomy is often used when bleeding persists, but preserving fertility is vital for some patients. CELOX gauze successfully controlled bleeding, offering a promising alternative to Bakri balloon tamponade. Further studies are needed to evaluate its role in standard care.

Keywords: postpartum hemorrhage, CELOX, hemostatic materials

OP-09

A case with Schinzel-Giedion syndrome

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Schinzel-Giedion Syndrome;

An ultra-rare multisystem disorder caused by gain-of-function pathogenic variants in a SETBP1 mutational hot spot,

- Global neurodevelopmental impairment, moderate-to-profound intellectual disability, epilepsy, hypotonia, hearing loss, and cerebral visual impairment.
- Poor weight gain
- Structural malformations can involve the heart, kidney/urinary tract, genitalia, brain.

To date, more than 50 individuals have been reported with molecularly confirmed classic SGS.

Patient; 31 yo, G2P1A1

Prenatal USG findings;

Nasal bone hypoplasia, ARSA, bilateral choroid plexus cysts, mitral regurgitation, HC 3.p., filum terminale cyst, larger than normal kidneys (75 mm at birth), global urinary tract dilatation (renal pelvis AP 13 mm max, the calyces were dilated), normal renal cortex thickness, polyhydramnios.

Amniosynthesis was performed; chromosome analysis and chromosomal microarray normal.

Prenatal pediatric surgery consultation:

Female fetus thought to have bilateral UPJ obstruction or bilateral VUR. Because of the filum terminale cyst, VUR caused by neurgenetic bladder is the preliminary diagnosis. Postnatal workup and surveillance recommended.

Postnatal first day, abdominal USG; bilateral renal enlargement (75mm bilaterally), and renal cortical thinning (1-6mm). Increased renal parenchymal echogenicity, bilateral grade 4 hydronephrosis, bilateral urethral dilatation in their whole length.

30.07.24 cystoscopy; bilateral urethers could not be catheterised. Then controlled with radio opaque substance, bilateral long distance obstructions were observed in the midurethral level.

21.08.2024; sleep EEG; frequent epileptiform activity. Diagnosed as West Syndrome.

WES trio was performed postnatally. Maternal and paternal WES was normal. The baby's WES result revealed; SETBP1 gene, heterozygous, probably pathogenic variant.

Keywords: Schinzel-Giedion Syndrome, Hydronephrosis, Whole genome sequencing

Bilateral Hydroureteronephrosis

Bilateral Hydroureteronephrosis

filum terminale cyst

filum terminale cyst

hydronephrosis

Hydroureteronephrosis

OP-10

Management of isolated fetal pleural effusion cases

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OBJECTIVE: This study aimed to evaluate obstetric and perinatal outcomes in isolated fetal pleural effusion (FPE) cases.

METHOD: This retrospective study included pregnant women with isolated FPE detected via ultrasonography at our clinic between January 2024-June 2024. The clinicodemographic characteristics and pregnancy outcomes were assessed.

RESULTS: Three isolated FPE cases (Case-1,2 and 3) were included. The Case-3 was diagnosed during prenatal follow-up for bilateral pes equinovarus. A prenatal invasive diagnostic test was offered to Case-3, who had a high combined risk in the dual screening test, the patient refused the procedure. All cases were diagnosed in the third trimester. No prenatal thoracoamniotic shunt or thoracentesis was performed. Case-1 showed spontaneous regression during intrauterine life. Case-3 was born preterm at 32 weeks due to fetal distress and the other cases were delivered at term. This preterm baby was admitted as an exitus in the 6th postnatal hour due to deep anemia and hemothorax after birth due to the picture that started with isolated bilateral FPE and progressed to fetal anemia and non-immune hydrops fetalis. Both babies born at term with isolated FPE in the prenatal period were healthy and no pathology was found in postnatal evaluation. Thoracentesis was performed in Case-2 and Case-3 in the postnatal period in whom spontaneous regression wasn't observed. One of these cases resulted in neonatal death and the other case had regression of effusion and clinical improvement after the procedure.

CONCLUSION: FPE is a rare finding and perinatal outcomes are more favorable in isolated cases.

Keywords: Pleural effusion, thoracentesis, thoracoamniotic shunt

Clinicodemographic characteristics, perinatal and postnatal outcomes of fetal pleural effusion cases

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Maternal age	25	32	31
Gravidity-Parity	G:1 P:0	G:4 P:3	G:2 P:1
Prenatal screening test	-	Low risk	High risk
FPE-US week of diagnosis	33	35	30
FPE-localization	Unilateral (Left)	Unilateral (Right)	Bilateral
FPE-largest diameter (mm)	53 mm	70 mm	Severe
Additional fetal anomalies	Isolated	Isolated	Bilateral pes ekinovarus Hidrops fetalis Polyhydramnios
Antenatal corticosteroid	Yes	Yes	Yes
Prenatal invasive diagnostic test	-	-	-
Mode of delivery	VD	C/S	C/S
Birth week	39	37	32
Birth weight	3100 g	2430 g	1790 g
APGAR 1st min.	7	5	4
APGAR 5th min.	8	6	6
Umbilical cord pH	-	7.2	6.8
Need for NICU	None	Present	Present
NICU hospitalization (day)	-	9	1
Postnatal invasive procedure	None	Thoracentesis	Thoracentesis
Spontaneous resolution of FPE	Present	-	-
Postnatal outcome	Healthy	Healthy	Neonatal death

OP-11

Ultrasonographic findings and clinical management of short rib thoracic dysplasia 18 with polydactyly: case report

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OBJECTIVE:

Short rib thoracic dysplasia 18 with polydactyly is an autosomal recessive skeletal ciliopathy characterized by narrow thorax, short costae, shortened long bones, polydactyly and frequently multi-organ system involvement. In this presentation, ultrasonographic findings and clinical management of a patient who was thought to have skeletal ciliopathy in prenatal screening will be evaluated.

METHOD: We aimed to present the case with ultrasonographic sections.

FINDINGS:

19-year-old primigravid patient was 24 weeks and 4 days pregnant according to LMP. In the ultrasonographic evaluation of our patient there was increased skin thickness in the face, neck and occipital region. Tubular extension was seen at the nasal location. There was hypertelorism and cleft palate/lip. The thorax was narrowed and the costae were shortened (Figure 1). Hepatomegaly, abdominal ascites and omphalocele were present. There was shortening of all long bones in bilateral upper and lower extremities (Figure 2). Brachydactyly and postaxial polydactyly were observed in the hands and feet with marked loss of ossification (Figure 3). The family was informed about genetic diagnostic tests and termination. Termination was performed in our patient who wanted to terminate her pregnancy (Figure 4-5). A tissue biopsy was taken from the abortion material for genetic examination. The molecular genetic report identified a variant in the IFT43 gene. The parents of the fetus were considered heterozygote carriers of this variant.

CONCLUSION: The family should be informed about diagnostic tests after ultrasonographic findings. Genetic counseling should not be limited to the fetus but should also include the parents.

Keywords: Short rib, Polydactyly, IFT43

Figure-1.

Small narrow thorax and distended abdomen on fetal sonogram

Figure-2.

Shortened and slightly curved femur on fetal sonogram

Figure-3.

Hand appearance on fetal sonogram

Figure-4.

Image of the terminated fetus. Cleft palate/lip, polydactyly, brachydactyly, edema on the cheek and neck.

Figure-5.

Fetal image on radiography. Shortness in all extremities, curvature of the fibula and short costae are seen

OP-12

Multidisciplinary Management of a High-Risk Pregnancy with Osler-Weber-Rendu Syndrome (Hereditary Hemorrhagic Telangiectasia), Behçet's Disease and Common Variable Immunodeficiency (CVID)

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INTRODUCTION: Osler-Weber-Rendu Syndrome, Behçet's Disease, and Common Variable Immunodeficiency (CVID) pose complex challenges during pregnancy. This case outlines the management of a pregnant patient with these comorbidities between 16 and 32 weeks.

Case Presentation: A 16-week pregnant woman diagnosed with Osler-Weber-Rendu syndrome, Behçet's Disease, and CVID presented with respiratory infection symptoms. In 2021, she underwent embolization for massive hemoptysis and cardiovascular surgery for endocarditis. She was on IVIG therapy and had previously been treated with prednisolone and colchicine.

During hospitalization, the patient was in an unpredictable condition requiring close monitoring, with recurrent episodes of hematemesis, hematochezia, melena, and bleeding from the left nostril and ear. A Chiari network in her right atrium increased thrombosis risk, complicating anticoagulation given her bleeding tendencies. Pregnancy monitoring focused on managing vascular and immune complications, while prednisolone and IVIG were administered, with attention to infection risks. Cardiovascular and pulmonary systems were also closely monitored.

Clinical Management:

- Cardiology: Monitored increased thrombosis risk due to Chiari network.
- Rheumatology: Managed Behçet's Disease with prednisolone and azathioprine.
- Pulmonology: Administered Pulmicort for asthma and monitored hemoptysis with sputum cultures.
- Hematology: Balanced anticoagulation with bleeding risk from Osler-Weber-Rendu.
- Immunology: Continued IVIG and steroid therapy for infection prevention and immune control.

At 32 weeks, fetal distress led to a cesarean section, delivering a 2040-gram neonate. Postnatal management included surgery for splenic bleeding. Both mother and neonate were stable upon discharge.

CONCLUSION: This case emphasizes the importance of multidisciplinary care in managing high-risk pregnancies with rare comorbidities.

Keywords: Osler-Weber-Rendu Syndrome, Behçet's Disease, Common Variable Immunodeficiency (CVID)

OP-13

A Rare case report diagnosis at 16th week: FATCO

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FATCO syndrome (Fibular Aplasia, Tibial Campomelia, Oligodactyly), first described by Hecht and Scott in 1981, is characterized by fibular aplasia or hypoplasia, tibial curvature or shortening, and oligosyndactyly. Although its etiology and genetic inheritance are not fully understood, it is mostly sporadic, with reports of autosomal dominant and X-linked inheritance. The prevalence is less than 1 in 1,000,000.

Differential diagnoses include FFU (Femur-Fibula-Ulna) complex, Fuhrmann syndrome (fibular aplasia, femoral curvature), and Split Hand/Foot Syndrome. In FATCO syndrome, advanced genetic testing, including Whole Exome Sequencing has shown that the regions of the WNT7A, TP63, and WNT10B genes are normal. Recent studies have identified a pathogenic variant in the DLX5 gene associated with this syndrome.

A 26-year-old primigravid woman with no teratogen, no radiation exposure and no consanguinity was referred to our center at 16 weeks of gestation. Ultrasound revealed that the biometrics were consistent with 16 weeks of gestation, a male fetus with absent left fibula, hypoplasia of the left tibia, a rudimentary left foot with oligodactyly, pes equinovarus. Other extremities were assessed as normal. A diagnosis of FATCO syndrome was made based on these findings. The patient was offered genetic testing and the option of pregnancy termination. Post-termination findings showed no metatarsal bones in the left foot, a two-digit structure, and pathology consistent with pes equinovarus.

Approximately 45 cases of FATCO syndrome have been described in the literature, with prenatal diagnosis being exceptionally rare. Our case is the earliest reported prenatal diagnosis at 16 weeks of gestation.

Keywords: fibular aplasia; FATCO; extremity

Figure 1: Ultrasound Image of Left Tibia and Fibular Aplasia

The ultrasound image of the left leg demonstrates the presence of the left tibia but the absence of the fibula, consistent with fibular aplasia. The tibial bone appears normal in structure, and no fibular structure is visible, confirming the diagnosis of fibular aplasia.

Figure 2: Ultrasound Image of Tibia with Fibular Aplasia and Abnormal Foot Rotation

The ultrasound image shows the presence of the tibia but an absence of the fibula, consistent with fibular aplasia. Additionally, there is abnormal rotation of the foot, indicating a malformation in limb alignment. These findings suggest a congenital limb anomaly affecting both the bones and the positioning of the foot.

Figure 3: Ultrasound Image of Baby's Foot with Oligodactyly and Syndactyly

The ultrasound image of the baby's foot shows oligodactyly, with fewer than five toes visible, and syndactyly, where two or more toes are fused together. These findings are consistent with congenital malformations (FATCO) affecting the development of the foot.

Figure 4: Post-Termination Image of Fetus with Leg Rotation and Clubfoot (Pes) Deformity

The image displays the leg of the fetus post-termination, exhibiting abnormal rotation and a clubfoot (pes) deformity. These findings are consistent with a congenital syndrome (FATCO), characterized by significant malformations in limb development. The abnormal rotation and foot positioning further confirm the diagnosis of a congenital anomaly.

Figure 5: Post-Termination Image of Baby's Foot with Oligodactyly and Syndactyly

The image shows the foot of the baby post-termination, clearly displaying oligodactyly, with fewer than five toes, and syndactyly, where two or more toes are fused together. These congenital abnormalities are consistent with the ultrasound findings, further confirming the diagnosis.

OP-14

Giant Fetal Neck Mass Case Report with Ex Utero Intrapartum Treatment (EXIT) Procedure

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INTRODUCTION: Ex utero intrapartum treatment (EXIT) procedures have been successfully used to manage various fetal airway obstructions, allowing for airway control at birth.

CASE: A 32-year-old woman, in her second pregnancy with one prior birth, was referred to us by an obstetrician at 31 weeks of gestation due to polyhydramnios and detection of a fetal neck mass on ultrasound.

Fetal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) performed at 31 weeks of gestation revealed a solid and cystic mass approximately 60×50×40 mm in size, extending from the submental area to the supraclavicular region, filling the lower oropharynx (Image1).

Emergency cesarean delivery were required at the 35th week of pregnancy due to rapidly developing fetal hydrops fetalis. The EXIT procedure was planned by a Perinatologist, a Neonatologist, an anesthesiologist, an otolaryngologist and a Pediatric Surgeon.

After the Kerr incision was opened during the EXIT procedure, both Kerr areas were circularly sutured without rupturing the amniotic membrane, and approximately 1900 cc of amniotic fluid was drained from the Kerr line.

After the delivery of the fetal head and single shoulder, fetal intubation and monitoring were started first. While oxygenation was provided by uteroplacental circulation, orotracheal intubation was achieved at the 25th minute. (Image 2). A 2875g male fetus was delivered with Apgar scores of 1 at the 1st minute and 0 at the 5th minute.

The histopathology of the mass was consistent with teratoma.

CONCLUSION: EXIT is an important method that provides advanced resuscitation in giant neck masses with high mortality and morbidity.

Keywords: Intrapartum treatment, Fetal neck masses

Image 1

Image 2

Image 3

OP-15

A rare anomaly: Tricuspid atresia-VSD, double outlet left ventricle and situs inversus totalis

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INTRODUCTION: Tricuspid atresia (TA) is a rare condition, occurring in 0.8 out of 10,000 live births. TA is classified as a congenital heart defect, leading to a functionally univentricular heart due to atrioventricular atresia. TA is characterized by the absence of the right atrioventricular connection, resulting in a lack of communication between the right atrium and the right ventricle (RV). There are three types of TA based on the spatial orientation of the great vessels (GV). Type 1 occurs in 70% to 80% of cases and is associated with normally oriented great arteries (aorta from left ventricle(LV) and pulmonary artery(PA) from RV). Type 2 occurs in 12% to 25% of cases and is associated with D-transposition of the GVs. Type 3, which is rare, is seen in the remaining TA cases and usually involves complex GV abnormalities, such as truncus arteriosus or L-transposition.

CASE: A 26-year-old patient with G3P1Y1A1, and an otherwise unremarkable medical history, was referred to our clinic from an external center due to suspicion of a cardiac anomaly. Following an ultrasonography, the patient was diagnosed with situs inversus totalis, type 3 TA-VSD, and double outlet LV. Subsequently, the patient developed aortic coarctation, with no additional anomalies detected.

DISCUSSION: In cases of TA-VSD, if the aorta is narrower than the PA in prenatal ultrasonography, ventriculoarterial discordance should be considered. In cases with a wide PA in TA, a postpartum PA banding operation is performed to prevent pulmonary hypertension.

Keywords: TA-VSD, DOLV

3 Vessel-Trachea

4 Chamber

Aort outlet

DOLV

PA outlet, VSD

OP-16

Emergency Rescue Cervical Cerclage With Bulging Membranes: Evaluation Of Four Cases In The Light Of The Literature

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The aim of this study is to examine the maternal and perinatal outcomes of four patients to whom we performed emergency cerclage with the diagnosis of membrane prolapsed cervical insufficiency in the second trimester of pregnancy. This retrospective study was conducted by evaluating patients with a previous history of premature birth, singleton pregnancies between 16-24 weeks, diagnosed with cervical insufficiency, and amniotic membrane prolapsed into the vagina. All patients were treated with bed rest, antibiotic prophylaxis, indomethacin tocolysis, cerclage suture using the McDonalds method, and postoperative micronized progesterone treatment. The average cervical dilatation amount of the patients at the time of admission was 6.7 cm, the average gestational week was 21w2d, and the average pregnancy duration after treatment was determined as 50.7 days. Two of the patients were treated with mersilene and silk sutures, and the other two were treated with a single mersilene suture. The average gestation period was 66 days in patients with 2 sutures, and 35.5 days in patients with a single suture. Three of the patients developed PPRM and premature birth occurred. One of the patients reached term and birth occurred at the 37th week of pregnancy. All patients gave live birth, and perinatal death occurred in 3 of them. In our study, it was determined that emergency cerclage applications prolong the pregnancy period. However, the positive contribution of the time gained with emergency cerclage to perinatal outcomes has not been determined.

Keywords: emergency cervical cerclage, cervical insufficiency, prematurity

Table 1

Patient	Age	Gravida	Living	Abortus
1	24	3	0	2
2	34	1	0	0
3	31	2	1	0
4	29	4	0	3
Mean/Standard deviation	29.5±4.2	2.5±1.2	0.25±0.5	1.25±1.5

Demographic and clinical characteristics of the cases

Table 2

Patient	Pregnancy week	Cervical dilation (cm)	Suture material	Number of sutures	Pregnancy period after treatment (day)
1	19w1d	8	mersilene	1	20
2	22w6d	7	mersilene, silk	2	15
3	20w1d	7	mersilene, silk	2	117
4	23w0d	5	mersilene	1	51
Mean/Standard deviation	21w2d±2d	6.7±1.2		1.5±0.5	50.7±46.9

Comparison of patients according to the amount of cervical dilation, suture properties used and pregnancy period after cerclage

Table 3

Patient	Gestational age at birth	Cause of birth	Type of birth	Live birth	Viability
1	22w0d	PPROM	normal vaginal birth	1	postnatal day 7 ex
2	25w0d	PPROM	cesarean section	1	postnatal day 14 ex
3	37w0d	Painful pregnancy at term	cesarean section	1	living
4	29w2d	PPROM	cesarean section	1	postnatal day 19 ex
Mean/Standard deviation	28.2±6.5			1±0	postnatal day 16.5 ex±6 day (except living)

Comparison of patients in terms of week of birth, cause of birth, type of delivery and fetal survival

OP-17

A Rare Condition Identified by Prenatal Diagnosis: Fetal Adrenal Hemorrhage

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Fetal adrenal hemorrhage (FAH) is a rare prenatal finding, with limited data available on its perinatal outcomes. The incidence of FAH is estimated to be around 1.7 per 1000 births. A literature review revealed that a total of 226 prenatally visualized fetal adrenal masses have been reported, with 45% (102 cases) confirmed as FAH. Prenatal diagnosis can be challenging, as its sonographic appearance may resemble other pathological conditions. Abdominal sonography has facilitated the diagnosis, especially when the clinical picture is unclear.

We report a case of a 34-year-old woman, G2P1, at 38 weeks of gestation, referred to our clinic due to a suspected abdominal mass and polyhydramnios. Ultrasound revealed a 43x34x38 mm cystic mass with septations in the left adrenal region, suggestive of FAH. The patient delivered a male infant via cesarean section at 39 weeks, with no abnormal clinical findings postnatally. Neonatal abdominal ultrasound showed a 3 cm semi-solid lesion in the left adrenal region with thick walls and dense septa, with no significant vascularity on Doppler, indicating an adrenal hematoma. Conservative management was chosen, and follow-up continues.

Prenatal FAH diagnosis is rare, and its exact pathogenesis remains unclear. The adrenal gland's vascular structure makes it prone to hemorrhage. Differential diagnosis includes neuroblastoma and other abdominal masses. Prognosis in the neonatal period is generally favorable, with most hematomas resolving spontaneously.

In conclusion, prenatal ultrasound, supported by postnatal imaging, plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and management of FAH. Careful monitoring in the neonatal period is essential for optimal outcomes. Conservative management is typically effective, with most cases resolving spontaneously.

Keywords: Fetal adrenal hemorrhage (FAH), Prenatal diagnosis, Adrenal hematoma

Cystic Content with Septations: Consistent with Adrenal Hemorrhage

This ultrasound image shows the cystic content and prominent septations consistent with adrenal hemorrhage. The septal structures within the mass and its semi-solid appearance are key findings supporting the diagnosis of adrenal hemorrhage. The septations reflect the characteristic sonographic features of the hemorrhage.

Axial View of Fetal Adrenal Hemorrhage

The axial ultrasound image shows a cystic mass in the left adrenal region, measuring approximately 38.37 mm by 32.39 mm. The mass exhibits fine septations, consistent with the sonographic features of a fetal adrenal hemorrhage. The dimensions are clearly marked, providing insight into the size and extent of the lesion at the time of evaluation.

Sagittal Plane: Location of the Cyst

The sagittal Plane plane ultrasound image shows the location of the cyst in the left adrenal region. The cyst appears as a well-defined structure, consistent with an adrenal hemorrhage. Its position relative to surrounding anatomical landmarks, including the kidney, further supports the diagnosis of a cystic adrenal hemorrhage.

Doppler Ultrasound in Coronal Plane: Renal Perfusion and Location of Adrenal Hemorrhage

The Doppler ultrasound image in the coronal plane shows the renal perfusion and the region corresponding to the left adrenal gland. A mass with no significant vascularity is observed in the area where the adrenal gland is located, consistent with an adrenal hemorrhage. The color Doppler highlights the renal blood flow clearly, while the adrenal mass shows no detectable blood flow.

OP-18

Mulibrey nanism, a rare cause of non immune hydrops fetalis

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Mulibrey Nanism(MUL) is an autosomal recessive disease caused by mutations in the TRIM37 gene with early onset fetal growth restriction and multiorgan dysfunction,including multiple organ abnormalities.Mulibrey is an acronym that stands for muscle, liver, brain, and eye. Exact incidence remains unknown due to the scarcity of identified cases.

We reported a prenatal diagnosis of MUL case associated with non immune hydrops fetalis.

A 26-year-old healthy primigravida woman, with a third-degree consanguinity with her husband, was referred to us at 18 weeks because of fetal ascites. Rest of the obstetric and family history was uneventful.Ultrasound demonstrated fetal ascites, pleural and pericardial effusion, thick nuchal fold and early onset fetal growth restriction.Infection screening (toxoplasma, cytomegalovirus, parvovirus and listeria) was negative.Also other causes of non immune hydrops fetalis were ruled out.

An amniocentesis was performed and genetic results revealed homozygous mutation in the TRIM37 gene. Although the family was informed about the unfavorable prognosis of the disease,the family chose to continue pregnancy.

At subsequent weekly scans, the ascites and pleural effusion increased.During ultrasound scans, decreased fetal movements secondary to fetal hypotonia, hepatomegaly, hypertelorism, frontal bossing and unilateral ventriculomegaly were noted.Magnetic resonance imaging at 27 weeks confirmed the presence of ascites, hepatomegaly, ventriculomegaly, atypical hypertelorism and an increased nuchal fold.

Unfortunately the fetus died at 28 weeks. A baby girl was delivered with a length of 32 cm and a weight of 1000 g by labour induction.Family rejected autopsy.

Consanguineous marriage is still one of the most important causes of fetal/neonatal mortality and morbidity.

Keywords: Anomaly, Genetics, Ultrasound

Fetal MRI at 27 weeks

Large placenta and severe ascites

Unilateral ventriculomegaly with irregular ventricle wall

OP-19

Prenatally Diagnosed Neuroblastoma- A Case Report

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With the advances in prenatal ultrasound screening technologies, the power of obstetric ultrasound to recognize fetal abdominal masses is increasing. Although masses detected during routine evaluations are rare, they are important in the differential diagnosis in terms of childhood malignancies. Neuroblastomas are among the most common tumors among childhood cancers. They can be diagnosed in the 3rd trimester of pregnancy, those diagnosed in the prenatal period tend to be small and 90% are of adrenal origin. Long-term survival of prenatally diagnosed neuroblastomas is 90% or more. In our case report, a fetal abdominal mass was detected at 36 weeks of gestation during routine antenatal follow-up. The postnatal ultrasonography of the patient, who was delivered at term, was reported as 'a mass lesion approximately 4x3 cm in size in the anteromedial of the left kidney with a cystic component accompanied by hemorrhagic leveling, containing a predominantly solid component accompanied by increased vascularity on RDUS examination' in accordance with the prenatal ultrasonography. The newborn was operated on postnatal day 11 and a 4x3x2.5 cm surrenal mass was excised. The final pathology result of the mass was poorly differentiated neuroblastoma. Although there is no indication for intrauterine intervention in neuroblastomas, it is important to perform the evaluations in the early period in order to make a definitive diagnosis in the postnatal period. In the prenatal period, these masses are usually diagnosed in the third trimester and should be kept in mind during routine obstetric imaging, especially when evaluating the fetal abdomen.

Keywords: fetal abdominal mass, neuroblastoma

Figure 1

fetal surrenal mass

OP-21

Ultrasonographic Findings And Clinical Management Of A Case Of Thoracopagus in Monochorionic Multiple Pregnancy: Case Report

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OBJECTIVE: Conjoined twins are a monoamniotic multiple pregnancy in which body parts of one twin are fused with the same body parts of the other twin. They are classified as cephalopagus, thoracopagus, omphalopagus, ischiopagus, parapagus, craniopagus, rachipagus and pygopagus according to the site of fusion. In this presentation, ultrasonographic findings and clinical management of a patient who was evaluated as thoracopagus in prenatal screening will be analysed.

RESULTS: A 33-year-old multiparous (G6P4A1) patient was 12 weeks and 6 days pregnant according to the last menstrual period. Ultrasonographic evaluation of the patient revealed a monochorionic twin pregnancy. The fetuses were observed as united in the thoracic region (Figure 1,2). The nuchal thickness of the 1st fetus was 4.5 mm and the nuchal thickness of the 2nd fetus was 4.7 mm (Figure 1). Lower and upper extremities were observed separately. The heart of both fetuses was observed in common (Figure 1,2,3). Extensive oedema was observed on the skin. The umbilical cord entrances were observed separately. The family was informed about genetic diagnosis tests and termination. Termination was applied to our patient who wanted to terminate her pregnancy (figure-4). The patient aborted vaginally.

CONCLUSION: In these rare cases, difficulties are encountered in both antenatal counselling and management of pregnancy. In addition to ultrasonographic findings, the family should be informed about prenatal diagnostic tests. It is important to increase awareness among clinicians.

Keywords: Multiple pregnancy, Thoracopagus

Figure-1. Increased nuchal translucency and common heart

Figure-2. Thoracophagus in 3D rendering image

Figure-3. Common heart structure and circulation in Glassbody mode view

Figure 4. Abortion material

OP-22

Congenital Sodium Diarrhea: A Case Report

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INTRODUCTION: Congenital Sodium Diarrhea (CSD) due to SLC9A3 mutation is a rare cause of neonatal diarrhea explained by dysfunction of the Na⁺/H⁺ antiporter 3 in intestine. Prenatal ultrasound findings are polyhydramnios and diffuse intestinal dilatation. Main differential diagnose is intestinal obstruction.

CASE: Age 26, gravid 1 pregnant was referred to our clinic because of the fetal polyhydramnios and intestinal dilatation. Diffuse intestinal dilatation and high level polyhydramnios were determined on ultrasound findings at first examination (Figure 1). According to these findings intestinal atresia and congenital diarrheas are suspected. As cesarean planned patient during term pregnancy had fetal bradycardia in 33rd week, female baby was given birth by urgent cesarean with the score of 5/8 APGAR, birth weight 2480 gr. The baby was operated with suspicion of intestinal atresia postnatal 3rd day and intestinal atresia was not determined during the operation. During the bowel biopsy the ganglion was seen and colostomy was carried out. The stool was coherent with sodium diarrhea. As SLC9A3 homisigote mutation was determined, diagnosis of congenitale sodium diarrheas was confirmed whole exome sequencing (WES). Actual test related to SLC9A3 genom applied to the parents.

Conclusion: Diffuse intestinal dilatation and polyhydramnios in fetal ultrasound may suggest congenital diarrheas. Detailed evaluation should be performed to prevent unnecessary surgery in these babies.

Keywords: SLC9A3 mutation, sodium diarrhea, polyhydramnios

Figure 1

2D ultrasound image of fetus: Diffuse intestinal dilatation

OP-23

Peroperative uterine packing with chitosan-covered tamponade to treat placental bed bleeding in a case of placenta previa

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Some biocompatible macromolecules obtained from plant/animal and microbial sources have led to significant positive contributions to quality of surgical care in recent decades. Among these biopolymers such as collagen, cellulose, one polysaccharide -chitosan- came to the forefront with its safety, antimicrobial, adhesive and hemostatic properties. This non-toxic polysaccharide is derived from main structural element in exoskeleton of insects and crustaceans: Chitin.

Chitosan-covered tamponade was originally used in military medicine by combining anti-hemorrhagic effect of chitosan and compressive effect of tamponade. Today, its use is more widespread. Chitin for the gauze is obtained from a species of shrimp -*Pandalus borealis*- and later modified to obtain its unique mode of action by protonation of the amine group of cationic polymer. Lately, it's applied primarily for post-partum hemorrhage and reported to reduce peripartum hysterectomy rates by 75%. The product absorbs water to form a gel adhering to surrounding tissues. Concurrently, its cationic nature attracts negatively charged erythrocytes creating a pseudo-clot. Resulting adhesive gel patch acts as a physical barrier to blood loss and works independently of the clotting cascade without entering blood circulation.

Hereby, we present a case of 22 year-old, gravida-2, parity-1 women with placenta previa undergoing elective cesarean at 37th week. Chitosan-covered gauze was applied intraoperatively to stop profuse bleeding from placental bed after removal. Following extraction of product after 24 hours, rest of post-operative period was uneventful. This case, presented in technical-visual details, inspired us about chitosan-covered gauze as a safe and effective alternative to commonly used technique of balloon-tamponade.

Keywords: Post-partum hemorrhage, chitosan-covered gauze

OP-24

Differential diagnosis of seizure in a hypertensive pregnant women: a case report

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Eclamptic seizures may develop in patients followed up for hypertension during pregnancy. Differential diagnosis of generalized seizures occurring in patients followed up for hypertension during pregnancy is essential due to the importance of eclamptic seizures. In our presentation, we aimed to explain the process of excluding eclamptic seizure and differential diagnosis of the patient who was followed up due to hypertension during pregnancy after a sudden generalized seizure. 24y G1P0Y0 26w pregnant. The patient was hospitalized for TA regulation and definitive diagnosis after the blood pressure value was found to be 160/100 in routine outpatient clinic control. Although the patient's ward TA follow-ups were normotensive, protein was found to be negative in the 24hour urine. There was no abnormality in the patient's routine laboratory tests. The patient had a generalized seizure during the ward follow-up, the patient had no known history of epilepsy, the patient was consulted to neurology, MR cerebral venography was planned, the patient had 2 nosebleeds during this process, likewise, she had no previous nosebleeds in her history. Emergency surgery was planned by the neurosurgeon for the patient who has detected to have a mass creating a shift effect in the right frontotemporal area in the MRI imaging.

Seizures during pregnancy, especially in hypertensive patients, primarily suggest eclampsia. However, other etiological causes such as "Cerebrovascular accident, Space-occupying central nervous system lesions, Epilepsy, Metabolic disorders, Infectious diseases, Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura" may rarely cause convulsions or generalized seizures and should be considered in the differential diagnosis of eclampsia.

Keywords: Seizure, preeclampsia, differential diagnosis

MRG images

OP-25

A rare diagnosis in pregnancy: chronic aortic dissection

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OBJECTIVE: Discussion of the management of a case of Type 3 aortic dissection in pregnancy.

FINDINGS: A 35-year-old G5P4 patient, at 32 weeks pregnant, presented with persistent back pain. She has a type 3 chronic aortic dissection, diagnosed at the 17th week of pregnancy. After a thorough assessment, a conservative management approach was adopted, with careful monitoring.

At 33 weeks 4 days of pregnancy, patient reported a severe headache, worsening back pain, and mildly elevated blood pressure. She underwent evaluation by a multidisciplinary team consisting of cardiology, cardiovascular surgery, and perinatology. To ensure maternal and fetal well-being, an elective cesarean section was planned in order to avoid increased intra-abdominal pressure; followed by cardiovascular surgery after the patient was stabilized. Betamethasone and magnesium sulfate therapy was planned prior to the cesarean section. Following the delivery of a healthy 2120 g male baby with an APGAR score of 9 at one minute and 10 at five minutes, the patient underwent cerebral debranching and ruptured aortic arch repair after twenty days.

CONCLUSION: This case emphasizes the challenges of managing pregnancy in patients with pre-existing aortic dissection. A multidisciplinary approach is essential for optimal care, with close monitoring of both maternal and fetal well-being. The decision to proceed with surgery or conservative management requires careful consideration, balancing the risks and benefits for both the mother and the fetus. These cases are especially rare in the young patient group, particularly in pregnant women, but should be considered especially in cases with persistent back pain.

Keywords: pregnancy, type 3 aortic dissection

OP-26

From physiological umbilical hernia to Beckwith-Wiedemann Syndrome

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A 28-year-old, G4P3Y3 patient was admitted to the clinic. She had physiological umbilical hernia, and her double test result was low risk. At the 15th week follow-up, it was observed that the physiological hernia had still not resolved and a diagnosis of omphalocele was made. Amniocentesis were recommended as prenatal diagnosis options, but they refused. They had a NIPT test done and the result was reported as a normal karyotype. During USG follow-ups, polyhydramnios developed in the baby, and omphalocele, hypospadias + testicular hydrocele were detected. At the 36th week, PPROM developed and she underwent C/S. Enlarged tongue, skin tag on the cheek in front of the ear, omphalocele, hypospadias and hydrocele were detected. The baby's genetic result was reported as BWS.

Omphalocele is a midline abdominal wall defect of variable size at the base of the umbilical cord. Cord/umbilical vessels typically sit at the top of the sac containing herniated abdominal contents [1]. Omphalocele is categorized as liver-free (containing loops of intestine) or liver-involving and if it not involve the liver are more associated with aneuploidia and are most commonly accompanied by BWS and trisomy 13 [1]. BWS is characterized by neonatal hypoglycemia, macroglossia, macrosomia, visseromegaly, different ear anomalies, and omphalocele, which is seen in 1/13700 live births. [2, 3] Genetic defect is the insulin-like growth factor II gene, which is located within the 11P15.5 region and may be responsible for organomegaly [2, 3]. BWS should be kept in mind in patients whose physiological umbilical hernia does not regress.

Keywords: Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome, omphalocele, hypospadias

Figure 1

Omphalocele appearance at 28 weeks with 2D ultrasonography

Figure 2

Omphalocele appearance at 28 weeks with 3D ultrasonography

Figure 3

Postnatal omphalocele appearance

OP-27

INV(5)(q15q33) IN BOTH PARENTS ASSOCIATED WITH RECURRENT PREGNANCY LOSS

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Recurrent pregnancy loss is defined as two or more pregnancy losses before the 24th week of gestation. RPL is a multifactorial condition¹. In %3-8 of RPL couples at least one parent is affected by a chromosomal abnormality². Inversion is a balanced structural chromosome anomaly defined as a break in two points on a chromosome, where the broken segment turns 180° and re-inserts into the same region. Inversion carriers are usually phenotypically normal and fertile. However, unbalanced gamete formation due to disorders in homologous chromosome pairing and recombination during meiosis can lead to clinical consequences such as infertility, RPL and offspring with congenital anomalies³. In the case report, the couple, who were first cousins, had two miscarriages. In the chromosome analysis, the same anomaly, inv(5)(q15q33), was detected in both parents. It is essential to perform karyotype analysis on couples who apply with RPL complaints. Since there is a risk of unbalanced gamete formation in couples carrying balanced structural chromosomal anomalies such as inversion, genetic counselling should be provided regarding preimplantation genetic diagnosis and prenatal genetic tests.

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Keywords: Recurrent pregnancy loss, Inversion

inv5 figure1

inv5 pedigree

OP-28

Case Presentations of Urorectal Septum Malformation

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Urorectal Septum Malformation (URSM) consists of urogenital, colon, and lumbosacral anomalies, along with the absence of perineal and anal openings. Partial URSM is a mild form in which feces and urine exit through a common perineal opening [1]. Complete URSM is fatal [2]. This article presents the sonographic findings and management of patients diagnosed with URSM in our institution.

Case 1

A 38-year-old patient was diagnosed with megacystis at 15 weeks of gestation. Amniocentesis revealed a normal 46,XY karyotype. At 28 weeks, a cesarean section was performed due to preterm labor. Physical examination showed no urethral or anal openings were observed. The pediatric surgery team performed colostomy and vesicostomy. The child is currently 5 years old.

Case 2

A 37-year-old patient was diagnosed with megacystis at 13 weeks on ultrasound. Chorionic villus sampling (CVS) revealed a normal 46,XX karyotype. At 15 weeks and 1 day, ultrasound detected absent renal parenchyma. As the fetus was not a candidate for intrauterine surgery, the patient chose to terminate the pregnancy. Post-abortion examination revealed no urethral or rectal openings in the fetus.

Antenatal diagnosis of URSM is challenging. Complete URSM is incompatible with life; however, partial URSM allows for survival if timely urological and surgical interventions are performed.

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Keywords: Urorectal Septum Malformation, prenatal diagnosis

OP-29

Right Atrial Isomerism, A Rare Case Report

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OBJECTIVE: The aim is to review the clinical features of a rare anomaly, right atrial isomerism, in a case that was referred to our clinic for detailed ultrasound and underwent pregnancy termination, in conjunction with literature review.

INTRODUCTION: Right atrial isomerism is characterized by the presence of 'double' right-sided structures and the underdevelopment or absence of left-sided structures. The juxtaposition of the aorta and inferior vena cava is a common feature in right atrial isomerism. Intracardiac anomalies are found in almost all cases of right atrial isomerism. Common cardiac defects in right atrial isomerism include a single ventricle, dextrocardia, AVSD, and an association with pulmonary stenosis or atresia. Asplenia is observed in 74% of right atrial isomerism cases. The prognosis for right atrial isomerism is typically worse than that for left atrial isomerism.

CASE: A 33-year-old multigravid patient at 21 weeks of gestation presented to our perinatology clinic for a detailed ultrasound. On ultrasound examination of the patient, who had no significant findings in her family, medical, or obstetric history, the following were observed: dextrocardia, midline-positioned stomach, persistent right umbilical vein, large AVSD, and possible pulmonary stenosis. Right atrial isomerism was suspected. The family was informed about the poor prognosis of the pregnancy and termination was recommended. At the family's request, the termination procedure was performed.

RESULT: Right atrial isomerism is a rare anomaly with an unknown etiology and a poor prognosis. Early ultrasound diagnosis allows for the option of early termination to be offered to the family, thereby minimizing the risks of maternal medical and psychological trauma.

Keywords: heterotaxy, atrial isomerism, ultrasound

Dextrocardia, Large AVSD

Endocardial Fibroelastosis

Juxtaposition Aort and IVC

The juxtaposition of the aorta and inferior vena cava is a common feature in right atrial isomerism.

Persisten Right Umbilical Vein, Midline-Positioned Stomach

The aorta and pulmonary artery arise from the right ventricle.

OP-30

A Rare Heart Anomaly: Familial Non-Compaction Cardiomyopathy

Abdullah Tabakci, Mucize Eric Ozdemir

Zeynep Kamil Kadın ve Çocuk Hastalıkları Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi

Isolated left ventricular non-compaction cardiomyopathy (LVNC) is a rare disorder, classified as a primary genetic cardiomyopathy. Diagnostic criteria are a) Absence of additional cardiac anomalies b) The ratio of the endocardial non-compact layer to the thin epicardial compact layer >2 c) Multiple trabeculations with deep endomyocardial recesses d) Direct blood flow from the ventricular cavity into the spaces between the prominent trabeculations

A 36 year old pregnant with a history of a previous baby who died at 6 months of life due to LVNC applied to our clinic at 23rd weeks of gestation. LVNC was detected by the fetal echocardiography. The mother was diagnosed with LVNC for the first time after parental cardiological examination we suggested. Maternal genetic work-up revealed non-pathogenic variants in the SCN5A1 and ACTC1 genes in molecular analysis. The same variants were also detected in the fetus.

The SCN5A gene encodes the major sodium channel in heart. ACTC1 gene is a sarcomeric gene that encodes the cardiac alpha-actin protein. Mutation of other variants of these genes have been reported to be associated with LVNC. These genes have autosomal dominant inheritance, and may show incomplete penetrance, which causes intrafamily variability.

Family members with the same mutation have a wide clinical spectrum. It may be asymptomatic or may lead to prenatal/neonatal death, heart failure, embolism, arrhythmia and sudden death. Other family members should be offered cardiological examination and genetic research as early diagnosis may prevent severe complications and neonatal death.

Keywords: non-compaction, SCN5A, ACTC1

LVNC

Endocardial non-compact layer/ Epicardial compact layer >2

LVNC Color Doppler

Direct blood flow into the recessus

OP-31

Prenatal diagnosis of Beckwith-Wiedemann Syndrome

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OBJECTIVE: Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome (BWS) is a rare autosomal dominantly inherited syndrome characterized by macroglossia, macrosomia, omphalocele, organomegaly, hemihyperplasia and renal malformations. We aimed to present the diagnosis of rare BWS in the prenatal period. **Case presentation:** A 26-year-old pregnant woman was referred to our Perinatology clinic due to polyhydramnios and increased nuchal fold thickness at 23 weeks of gestation. The parent had no any genetic disease. There was no consanguinity and their previous children were healthy. In fetal ultrasonographic examination; In addition to polyhydramnios, there was hepatomegaly (liver longitudinal diameter; 50 mm (>95 mm)), dilatation of the gallbladder, bilateral renal pelviectasis, increased nuchal fold thickness (12.4 mm), macroglossia, and placentomegaly (diameter: 56 mm) (Figure 1-3). Genetic counseling for the fetus was recommended to the parents. Cytogenetic and microarray analysis were normal, but hypermethylation was detected in the BWS IC1 region and was evaluated as compatible with BWS. The family preferred termination of pregnancy.(Image 1) **CONCLUSION:** Polyhydramnios in early pregnancy may be associated with genetic diseases and is often accompanied by fetal developmental delay. Detailed sonographic examination for BWS findings in cases larger than the gestational week may be useful in identifying rare BWS cases in the prenatal period.

Keywords: Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome, macroglossia, prenatal diagnosis

FIGURE 1

increased nuchal fold thickness

FIGURE 2

dilatation of the gallbladder

FIGURE 3

bilateral renal pelviectasis

IMAGE 1

image of fetus with Beckwith-Wiedemann Syndrome

OP-32

A Case Report of Semilobar Holoprosencephaly with Malalignment Ventricular Septal Defect and Narrow Cisterna Magna

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OBJECTIVE:

The semilobar variant of Holoprosencephaly (HPE) is characterized by the presence of rudimentary lateral ventricles, partial development of the interhemispheric fissure, and incomplete formation of the falx cerebri, which is primarily visible posteriorly(1). This case report presents a fetus with semilobar HPE accompanied by malalignment ventricular septal defect (VSD), diagnosed in the first trimester.

CASE:

A 25-year-old gravida 6, para 2 patient, with three prior miscarriages and no consanguinity, presented for first-trimester ultrasound screening. The patient had no history of smoking or medication use. At 12 weeks and 6 days of gestation, the ultrasound revealed a fetus (figure 1) with semilobar HPE (figure 2), exophthalmos, hypertelorism, frontal flattening, malalignment VSD (figure 3), and a single umbilical artery. The patient was advised to undergo prenatal invasive diagnostic testing and consider termination of the pregnancy, declined further testing. Upon re-evaluation five weeks later, measurements: biparietal diameter of 15 weeks and 2 days, head circumference of 15 weeks and 3 days, abdominal circumference 18 weeks, and femur length consistent with 18 weeks and 3 days. Ultrasonography showed additional anomalies, including microcephaly, micrognathia, postaxial polydactyly, bilateral pes equinovarus. Amniocentesis revealed a normal karyotype (46/--), and prenatal microarray analysis detected no significant copy number variants. The pregnancy was terminated (figure 4), postnatal genetic testing confirmed the prenatal findings.

CONCLUSION: Semilobar holoprosencephaly is a severe congenital anomaly. When combined with other anomalies like malalignment VSD and microcephaly, it often results in a poor prognosis. Early detection allows for comprehensive prenatal counseling and informed decision-making.

Keywords: Semilobar holoprosencephaly, ventricular septal defect, prenatal diagnosis

Figure 1

At 12 weeks and 6 days of gestation, the ultrasound revealed a fetus with frontal flattening

Figure 2

Semilobar holoprosencephaly

Figure 3

Malalignment Ventricular Septal Defect

Figure 4

The fetus

OP-33

Thanatophoric Dysplasia Type 1: A Case Report

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OBJECTIVE:

Thanatophoric dysplasia (TD) is a common lethal skeletal dysplasia with an estimated incidence of 1 in 35,000 to 50,000 live births (1,2). Although TD follows an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern, most cases result from de novo mutations due to the fatal outcome of the disorder. Pulmonary hypoplasia, secondary to thoracic narrowing, is the primary cause of early postnatal mortality. Mutations in the fibroblast growth factor receptor 3 (FGFR3) gene are responsible for the condition(3).

CASE:

A 31-year-old gravida 2, para 1 patient, with no history of consanguinity or medication use, was referred to our clinic at 21+2 weeks of gestation for detailed ultrasound imaging. At 22+2 weeks, ultrasound findings revealed all fetal extremities measuring below the 1st percentile, with a femur length (FL) of 15+2 weeks and a humerus length (HL) of 16+0 weeks. The thorax/abdominal circumference ratio was less than 0.6, indicating thoracic hypoplasia. (Figure 1,2) Additional findings included frontal bossing (Figure 3) brachydactyly, and micromelia.(figure 4) The patient was advised to undergo prenatal invasive testing and consider termination. Chromosomal analysis revealed no abnormalities, but whole-exome sequencing identified a heterozygous FGFR3 mutation (p.R248C), consistent with type 1 TD. The pregnancy was terminated using a misoprostol protocol.

CONCLUSION: TD type 1 is a fatal skeletal disorder that can be diagnosed through detailed ultrasound imaging and molecular genetic analysis. Early detection enables healthcare professionals to counsel patients regarding the prognosis and management options. The presence of an FGFR3 mutation confirmed the diagnosis in this case and facilitated appropriate clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Thanatophoric dysplasia, FGFR3 mutation, pulmonary hypoplasia.

resim 1

thoracic hypoplasia

resim 2

thoracic hypoplasia

resim 3

frontal bossing

resim 4

the fetus

OP-34

Twin pregnancy complicated with *Listeria monocytogenes* infection: a rare case report

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Listeria monocytogenes is the facultative intracellular bacillus responsible for Listeriosis and the risk of infection is higher during pregnancy. Listeriosis in twin pregnancies is rare but devastating. A 33-year-old patient with a monochorionic diamniotic twin pregnancy of 25 weeks according to the transfer date was admitted to our hospital with high fever and fatigue. In consultation with the infectious diseases department, blood and urine cultures were taken from the patient and ceftriaxone treatment was started empirically. As *Listeria monocytogenes* grew in the blood culture, the patient was started on ampicillin-sulbactam 4x2gr treatment. Cranial MRI and echocardiography were requested for the patient to evaluate neurological and cardiac involvement. On the 10th day of hospitalization, one of the fetuses was observed to die in utero. No pathology was observed in the fetal doppler evaluation, but oligohydramnios developed in the living fetus. As the patient's infection parameters continued to increase meropenem was added to her treatment. After 6 days, it was observed that the other fetus also died in utero. Cytotec protocol was initiated for the patient and normal vaginal delivery was performed.

Following anti-infection therapy, the patient recovered well and was discharged with negative result of blood bacterial culture and normal inflammatory indicators. Symptoms of the *Listeria monocytogenes* infection in pregnancy are non-specific, which should be paid more attention in case of unexplained fever and fetal distress. The blood culture is effective for accurate diagnosis. Listeriosis remains one of the infections associated with the highest fetal and neonatal morbidity.

Keywords: *Listeria*, infection, pregnancy

OP-35

Recurrent cerebellar hypoplasia; Genetic testing is not always useful

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INTRODUCTION: Cerebellar hypoplasia is a neurological condition in which the cerebellum is smaller than usual or not completely developed. To the date, recurrent cerebellar hypoplasia is not reported in the literature.

CASE PRESENTATION: A 34-year-old multigravid patient at 22 weeks of pregnancy was admitted to our perinatology clinic for second trimester anomaly screening. The mother's medical and obstetric history revealed a previous child with a diagnosis of cerebellar hypoplasia. In the ongoing pregnancy, biometric measurements were compatible with 22 weeks, while the cerebellum was found to be compatible with 18 weeks (<2 SD). No additional findings rather than cerebellar hypoplasia were detected by the ultrasonography scan. The case underwent fetal invasive diagnostic testing together with magnetic resonance imaging. The fetal MRI result confirmed the cerebellar hypoplasia. The family was counseled about the poor prognosis. The termination procedure was performed without any complications. Both karyotype and whole exome sequencing test results were reported to be normal.

CONCLUSION: Detailed ultrasonographic evaluation during second trimester is very important for antenatal detection of fetal structural anomalies. The neurodevelopmental outcome is very poor for children with cerebellar hypoplasia. Thus, prenatal diagnosis of cerebellar hypoplasia provides appropriate pregnancy management. It is difficult to understand the the underlying genetic factors leading to recurrent cerebellar hypoplasia by the recent technologies.

Keywords: cerebellar hypoplasia, prenatal diagnosis

Figure 1: Ultrasonography image of cerebellar hypoplasia

Figure 2: MRI image of cerebellar hypoplasia

Figure 3: Fetal MRI sagittal image, normal vermis

OP-37

Mosaic Trisomy 20 and Corrected Transposition of the Great Artery: Case Report

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Complete trisomy 20 is rare and thought to be incompatible with life. However, mosaic trisomy 20, in which a portion of cells or tissues contain extra chromosomes, is one of the most common prenatally detectable mosaic trisomies. Due to the paucity of molecular study publications, it is still unclear whether the origin of the trisomy is in the fetus or in extraembryonic tissues and whether it affects neonatal outcomes. Trisomy 20 is associated with a normal phenotype in approximately 90-95% of cases, while approximately 5-10% are reported to have abnormal findings. These findings include unexplained fetal death, intrauterine growth retardation and multiple congenital anomalies. There may be a weak correlation between the percentage of trisomic cells found in the genetic analysis of amniocentesis and the risks to the newborn. However, even in the presence of high levels of trisomic cells, neonatal outcomes are usually normal, making it difficult to predict the prognosis and provide genetic counseling in patients with a mosaic pattern. We report a case of mosaic trisomy 20 diagnosed prenatally in cells cultured from amniotic fluid. Trisomy 20 was present in 8 (5.7 percent) of a total of 140 cells analyzed. Fetal echocardiography showed corrected transposition of the great artery, dextrocardia, interrupted inferior vena cava, continuity of the azygos vein and patent foramen ovale. In this report, we aimed to present a patient with corrected transposition of the great artery, a rare cardiac anomaly associated with mosaic trisomy 20.

Keywords: Trisomy 20 Mosaicism, Congenitally corrected transposition of the great arteries (CCTGA)

parallel course of great vessels

OP-39

Mechanical Valve Thrombosis in a Pregnant Women: A Case Report

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Mechanical heart valves are associated with an increased incidence of thromboembolic events during pregnancy. Therapeutic anticoagulation throughout pregnancy is essential to reduce the risk of thromboembolic complications. But given the absence of adequate prospective controlled trials and the differing maternal and fetal risks associated with various anticoagulants, the optimum anticoagulant regimen is uncertain. The choice of anticoagulation strategy is challenging. Pregnancy in women with mechanical heart valves is very high risk and has been classified by the World Health Organization as Risk Category III (significantly increased risk of maternal mortality or severe morbidity). Pregnant women with mechanical heart valves are at increased risk of serious maternal complications, including valve thrombosis, thromboembolism, hemorrhage, and death. The risk of poor fetal outcomes is also high, with increased rates of spontaneous abortion, fetal death, fetal hemorrhage, and teratogenicity related to Warfarin. For women with mechanical heart valves, the maternal mortality rate remains > 1% and the risk of valve thrombosis is approximately 5%. Pregnant women with a mechanical prosthesis should be monitored in a tertiary-care center with a dedicated multidisciplinary treatment of cardiologists, surgeons, anesthesiologists, hematologists and maternal-fetal medicine obstetricians with expertise in the management of high-risk cardiac conditions during pregnancy.

In this case report, we present a 11-week-pregnant patient in whom mechanical heart valve thrombosis developed during anticoagulation therapy with low molecular weight heparin and treated with tPA. Warfarin was started after tPA. At 36 weeks and 3 days, the patient was delivered by cesarean section.

Keywords: pregnancy, mechanical heart valve thrombosis, anticoagulation

mechanical heart valve thrombosis

OP-40

Surgical Resection of Obstructed Part of Robert's Uterus During Cesarean Section

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This article aims to share the happy ending journey of our patient with a rare uterine malformation. A Robert's uterus is a rare congenital abnormality, characterized by a uterus that has a single horn and an associated rudimentary horn that may or may not communicate with the main cavity. [1] Robert's uterus occurs due to a failure in the fusion of the Müllerian ducts during fetal development. This abnormal fusion results in the formation of a single, often non-functional, uterine horn. Robert's uterus can lead to complications such as infertility, ectopic pregnancy in the rudimentary horn, and higher risks during pregnancy. Women with this condition may require careful monitoring and management if they become pregnant.

Our patients suffered from infertility and painful menstrual periods due to the obliterated semi-right uterine cavity with an obstructed right fallopian tube. First, we performed hysteroscopy and laparoscopy to identify uterine conditions. We tried to resect the thick septum between uterine cavities to solve the problem but we could not succeed we made the current uterine cavity bigger and widened into the obstructed part.

After IVF treatment the patient got pregnant, we performed a cesarean section and we resected the maldeveloped part of the uterus and the right tube. After surgery, we gave the patient 3 sacs of blood transfusion. The patient was discharged with the baby on the 3rd postoperative day. The patient could have vaginal birth afterward uterine resection but she refused. Patient demand led to our method of delivery.

Keywords: Robert's Uterus, Cesarean section

after operation usg

photo shows the endometrial thickness in post 5th day.

first hsg

the first hsg before diagnosis of Robert's Uterus

happy ending

after cesarean section and endometrectomy first patient visit

intraoperative photo

obliterated endometrial cavity entrance

secondary HSG

after hysteroscopic enlargement of uterin cavity

suturing

suturing after total excision of endometrial cavity with its base layer.

OP-41

Identifying The Risk Factors And The Outcomes Of Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS): Data From A University Hospital Setting In Tirana, Albania

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INTRODUCTION: Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) is a life-threatening disorder that complicates 1 in 200 pregnancies. Over the last decades through various researches the increased rate of Cesarean deliveries has been identified as a risk factor related to abnormal placentation. This study aims to investigate the independent risk factors and outcomes of PAS.

MATERIALS-METHODS: This is a retrospective cohort of all cases admitted with the diagnosis of PAS during a five year period (2016 - 2022) in a tertiary referral center. Only cases that delivered at our institution were included. The cases were compared to a control group, selected by randomly picking 1 in 3 patients, comprised of women who delivered during the study period for whom the diagnosis of abnormal placentation was excluded. Univariate analysis were performed to predict possible risk factors and a multivariate logistic regression model was designed to predict the relation between Placenta Previa(PP), prior Cesarean Sections and IVF as independent risk factors for PAS.

RESULTS: 8028 deliveries were included in this analysis, of which 161 presented with a history of abnormal placentation. 1324 (16.5%) patients had a history of prior cesarean section and 136 (1.7%) had IVF pregnancies. PP ($p<0.0001$), prior C-sections ($p=0.009$) and IVF ($p=0.007$) were found to serve as independent risk factors for developing PAS.

CONCLUSION: There was a statistically significant association between a history of cesarean sections and occurrence of abnormal placentation. This relationship was dependent on the number of prior Cesarean Sections. IVF was identified as an independent risk factor.

Keywords: IVF, Cesarean Section

OP-42

Antenatal corticosteroids: a thoughtful and considered action!

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Since 1994, administration of ACS is recommended for all pregnant patients at 23+0 to 33+6 weeks of gestation who are at increased risk of preterm delivery within the next seven days. ACS improves neonatal survival and reduces major short-term morbidity, although long-term neurodevelopmental issues remain a concern. ACT Administration at $\geq 34+0$ wGA is controversial, because of less absolute respiratory benefit and greater concern about potential long-term harm! Data on long-term of ACT effects are limited. Increasing evidence from animal studies suggests that ACS administration promotes terminal differentiation of fetal organs in lieu of cell proliferation. These changes in the developmental program predispose the preterm neonate to the development of chronic disease such as diabetes, hypertension, heart failure, and psychiatric disorders. Concerns also remain regarding potential adverse effects on neurodevelopmental outcome, particularly with in utero exposure late in gestation. Disruption of the normal fetal environment at this critical time may lead to changes in development of the neuroendocrine system. The dose has not been challenged since Liggins experiment, so large randomised trials evaluating novel dose regimens are urgently needed, while most ACT fetuses are delivered at term, unnecessary exposed to lifelong consequences. After 50 years, we have to consider administration of ACS thoughtfully to improve corticosteroid timing and neonatal outcomes.

Keywords: antenatal corticoid administration

OP-43

Endothelial dysfunction, arterial stiffness, retinal microvasculature changes in high-risk preeclampsia women: Impact of smoking

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BACKGROUND: Preeclampsia (PE) significantly impacts maternal and neonatal health, with endothelial dysfunction and arterial stiffness central to its pathophysiology. Although smoking cessation improves cardiovascular health, its effects on high-risk pregnancies require further clarification.

MATERIALS-METHODS: This study evaluated endothelial function, arterial stiffness, and retinal microvasculature profile in 43 high-risk women, identified during first-trimester PE screening, comparing 18 previous smokers with 25 non-smokers. Measurements taken at 11–16 weeks (V1), 24–28 weeks (V2), and 34–37 weeks (V3) included asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), cotinine, heart rate (HR), mean arterial pressure (MAP), systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), pulse wave velocity (PWV), central retinal arteriolar equivalent (CRAE), central retinal venular equivalent (CRVE).

RESULTS: Both groups showed no significant differences in age ($p=0.312$) or BMI ($p=0.579$). Key findings from V2 to V3 include increased ADMA ($p=0.028$), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ($p=0.002$), mean arterial pressure (MAP) ($p=0.007$), HR ($p=0.001$), and systolic blood pressure (SBP) ($p=0.020$), along with decreased CRAE ($p=0.016$) and CRVE ($p=0.004$) in high-risk cohort. Non-smokers showed significant increases in ADMA ($p=0.006$), MAP ($p=0.037$), DBP ($p=0.019$), and HR ($p=0.006$). Previous smokers did not exhibit these changes, with no significant differences compared to non-smokers.

CONCLUSION: Early endothelial and retinal alterations are potential predictors of pregnancy-induced hypertension, particularly in high-risk cohorts. Our findings highlight the substantial benefits of smoking cessation on vascular health during pregnancy. This study emphasizes the importance of targeted screening and interventions for high-risk women to improve both maternal and fetal outcomes.

Keywords: Preeclampsia, Smoking, Vascular Health

OP-44

A case of colostomia bipolaris after a perineal rupture

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A 40-year-old primigravida was admitted to the hospital at 40 weeks of gestation with contractions occurring every 5 minutes, preparing for delivery. At 7 cm dilation, she was administered an intravenous infusion of 5 IU Syntocinon in 500 mL of 5% Glucose Solution. During the delivery, a lateral episiotomy was performed, and the baby was delivered with an Apgar score of 9/10. Following placental delivery, examination of the birth canal revealed a posterior vaginal wall rupture, involving the rupture of both the external and internal anal sphincters, as well as a 7 cm rectal rupture. Initial attempts to repair the ruptures were unsuccessful, necessitating the creation of a colostomy (sigmoidostomy). The patient was subsequently taken to the operating room for an infraumbilical median laparotomy, where the sigmoid colon was diverted to a stoma on the abdominal wall.

Three months later, the colostomy was reversed, and sigmoid colon anastomosis was successfully performed, resulting in functional bowel recovery. Postoperative follow-up examinations were satisfactory.

Although postpartum colon ruptures are exceedingly rare, they can occur even in otherwise healthy women. Accurate diagnosis and appropriate surgical management are essential for optimal patient outcomes

Keywords: perineal rupture, OASIS, colostomy

OP-47

Retrospective Analysis of Characteristics and Neonatal Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Intrauterine Fetal Blood Transfusion

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OBJECTIVE: The aim of this study was to evaluate the demographic and clinical characteristics and neonatal outcomes of patients who underwent intrauterine fetal blood transfusion (IFBT).

MATERIALS-METHODS: This retrospective analysis comprised 9 cases of IFBT conducted at the perinatology clinic of Ankara Etlik City Hospital from September 2022 to June 2024. The study analyzed demographic data, pregnancy features, diagnostic and treatment progress, and newborn outcomes.

RESULTS: The majority of patients who underwent IFBT were diagnosed with Rh D isoimmunization, with 5 cases and 2 cases involving human parvovirus b19 infection. The mean gestational age at the time of initial transfusion was 28 weeks, and patients received an average of 3 transfusions. On average, 4 transfusions were performed per patient with Rh incompatibility and 3 transfusions in patients infected with parvovirus. The mean MoM value of the middle cerebral artery peak systolic velocity was 1.8 in patients with Rh incompatibility and 1.85 in those with parvovirus infection. The mean gestational week at birth was 30 and the mean birth weight was 1988 gr. The neonatal survival rate was 66.67%. The complications including fetal distress and loss. One neonate was diagnosed with alpha-thalassemia and another with subgroup C incompatibility.

CONCLUSION: IFBT is an important treatment for severe fetal anemia and significantly improves fetal and neonatal outcomes. Early diagnosis and timely intervention are particularly important in the management of pregnancies complicated by rhesus incompatibility and other causes of fetal anemia.

Keywords: Fetal Anemia, fetal hydrops, intrauterine fetal blood transfusion

OP-48

Pregnancy during and after cancer treatment: experience of a single tertiary center

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OBJECTIVE: To investigate obstetric and perinatal outcomes among pregnant cancer patients and survivors.

MATERIALS-METHODS: A retrospective analysis of maternal and perinatal outcomes for pregnant women who either had a history of cancer or continued cancer treatment during pregnancy and received antenatal and prenatal care at Marmara University, Department of Perinatology, between January 2019 and August 2024 was conducted. Perinatal and maternal outcomes were assessed based on cancer type and treatment methods.

RESULTS: Seventeen patients were included in the study. Demographic data and results are shown in Table 1. The most frequently encountered tumor types in pregnant women with a history of cancer were hematologic malignancies (35.2%) and thyroid cancer (23.5%). The mean maternal age was 38.6 ± 7.03 years. The frequencies of delivery before 37 and 34 weeks were 29.4% and 11.7%, respectively. There was one fetal demise and three terminations of pregnancy among our patients. There were no congenital anomalies in our group.

CONCLUSION: Patients who became pregnant during or after cancer treatment had moderate to poor obstetric outcomes. The pregnancy follow-up for these patients should be carried out by a multidisciplinary team at tertiary centers. Although there appears to be no in utero fetal impact, we believe that long-term follow-up for both these patients and their offspring should be conducted to assess for any potential impacts including childhood cancers.

Keywords: Pregnancy, cancer, pregnancy outcomes

Table 1

Patient	Pregnancy Age	G/P	Diagnosis	Age at diagnosis	Treatment	Gestational Week at First Examination	Pregnancy Complications	Delivery Week	Delivery Method	Newborn Outcome
1	35	G6P3A1	Hodgkin Lymphoma	27	Remission	10+0W	Still Pregnant			
2	43	G1P0A1	Astrocytoma	43	levetiracetam, Temozolomid, RT	15+5W	Termination of Pregnancy			
3	41	G4P2A2	Metastatic Breast Cancer	41	CTX-RT	16+0W	Termination of Pregnancy			
4	33	G4P2A2	Papillary Thyroid Cancer	28	Total Thyroidectomy + RAI	35+4W	None	38+4	NSVD	NICU(31 days)
5	23	G3P2A1	Hodgkin Lymphoma	20	CTX (Completed 1.5 years ago)	38+0W	None	38+1W	C/S	Healthy
6	27	G1P1	Papillary Thyroid Cancer	22	Total Thyroidectomy +RAI	12+5W	None	42+1W	NSVD	Healthy
7	28	G7P2Y2	Papillary Thyroid Cancer	24	Total Thyroidectomy + RAI	7+1W	None	39+3W	C/S	Healthy
8	31	G3P2A1	Lung Cancer	21	CTX (5 sessions)	18+6W	None	35+5W	C/S	Healthy
9	39	G3P3	Cutaneous T Cell Lymphoma	39	No treatment	12+2W	Preeclampsia	Unknown	C/S	Healthy
10	27	G1P1	ALL	10	Bone Marrow Transplant	10+2W	Premature Rupture of Mem	32+4W	C/S	NICU (23 days)
11	31	G3P4A1	Hodgkin Lymphoma	29	Received 4 cycles of ABVD	12+2W	Macrosomia	40+4W	C/S	Healthy
12	31	G1P1	CML	26	Imatinib (not used during pregnancy)	22+6W	Vaginal Bleeding	36+3W	C/S	Healthy
13	34	G1P1	Thyroid Cancer	18	Total Thyroidectomy + RAI	23+0W	None	39+0W	NSVD	NICU(7 days)
14	39	G4P3A1	Breast Cancer	38	Mastectomy + CTX + RT (received during)	11+3W	Termination of Pregnancy			
15	37	G2P2	Leiomyosarcoma	37	TAH + BSO	21+4W	Placenta Previa	31+2W	C/S	NICU (35 days)
16	31	G1P0	Astrocytoma	31	Right parietal craniotomy + subtotal tumor resection	19W	None	34+3W	C/S	Healthy
17	28	G1P0	Astrocytoma	28	Median suboccipital craniotomy with tumor resection	20+6W	In utero demise	23W		0 Ex

CTX: Chemotherapy; RT: Radiotherapy; RAI: Radioactive iodine; TAH+BSO: Total abdominal hysterectomy and Bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy; NSVD:normal spontaneous vaginal deliver, CS:caesarean section, NICU: neonatal intensive Care Unit

OP-49

Comparison of Malformation Rates in Fetuses of Pregnant Women with Gestational Diabetes and Pregestational Diabetes: A Retrospective Cohort Study

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OBJECTIVE: Comparison of anomalies, obstetric and fetal outcomes in gestational diabetes and pregestational diabetes

MATERIALS-METHODS: The data of 600 pregnant women with gestational diabetes and 209 pregestational diabetes from September 2019 to September 2021 and their postpartum babies were retrospectively analyzed in this cohort study.

RESULTS: Pre-pregnancy and post-pregnancy weight, pre-pregnancy BMI, and post-pregnancy BMI values of the PGDM group were significantly higher than the GDM group. The week of birth of those in the PGDM group was substantially lower. The C/S ratio (79.9%) in the PGDM group was considerably higher than the rate in the GDM group (68.7%). The 1st-minute APGAR and 5th-minute APGAR scores of the PGDM group babies were significantly lower. There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of fetal complications, neonatal intensive care admissions, and stillbirths.

The incidence of minor genitourinary system anomaly in the PGDM group was found to be significantly lower than the rate in the GDM group. There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of other anomalies. In the GDM group, the rate of minor anomalies in those regulated by diet was significantly lower.

CONCLUSION: PGDM had slightly higher and sometimes significantly worse obstetric, perinatal, and fetal outcomes. Regardless of the specific outcomes, the key priority should be meticulous management and glycemic control for diabetic mothers to ensure the best possible health for both the mother and baby.

Keywords: Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Pre-gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Fetal Outcomes

OP-50

Maternal Outcomes of Pregnancy Terminations in Women with a History of Uterine Surgery: A Retrospective Analysis

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OBJECTIVE:

The aim of this retrospective study is to evaluate the maternal outcomes of pregnancy terminations performed in our clinic for fetal or maternal indications in women with a history of uterine surgery.

MATERIALS-METHODS: This study analyzes the data of 51 cases with a history of uterine surgery who underwent pregnancy termination. Inclusion criteria were a history of uterine surgery and termination performed in our hospital, while exclusion criteria included a history of vaginal delivery, primiparity, and termination conducted outside the hospital. In patients receiving misoprostol, the doses were determined according to the FIGO Guidelines for Misoprostol Use.

RESULTS: The mean gestational age at termination was 20.9 ± 5.9 weeks, and the mean maternal age was 33.1 ± 5.4 years. The incidence of uterine rupture was 3.9%, and 2% of the patients required a blood transfusion. The median misoprostol dose was 1600 mcg (range: 400-3200), and the median abortion duration was 14 hours (range: 4-40 hours). Among induction methods, misoprostol was the most commonly used, in 68.6% of cases, followed by Foley balloon in 3.9% and hysterotomy in 27.5% (Table 1). The most common indication for termination was central nervous system anomalies, reported in 37.2% of cases (Table 2).

CONCLUSION: Pregnancy terminations for fetal and maternal indications in women with a history of uterine surgery are associated with significant maternal morbidities, such as uterine rupture and the need for blood transfusion. These findings highlight the importance of careful management and close monitoring of these high-risk pregnancies, particularly as gestational age advances.

Keywords: termination, uterine surgery

Summary of Key Clinical Data for Pregnancy Termination Cases

Variable	Value
Gestational age (weeks)	20.9 ± 5.9
Maternal age (years)	33.1 ± 5.4
Gravida	3 (2-4)
Parity	2 (1-2)
Abortus	0 (0-1)

Living children	1 (1-2)
Number of previous Cesarean section	1 (1-3)
Uterine rupture	3.9%
Need for blood transfusion	2%
Misoprostol dose (mcg)	1600 (400-3200)
Abortion duration (hours)	14 (4-40)
Misoprostol	68.6%
Foley balloon	3.9%
Hysterotomy	27.5%

Values are given as median (min-max) or mean \pm standard deviation.

Termination Indications and Their Percentages

Indication	%
CNS anomaly	37.2
Aneuploidy	11.8
PPROM	11.8
Multiple anomalies	9.8
Cardiac anomaly	7.8
Genitourinary system anomaly	5.9
Chromosomal anomaly	3.9
Skeletal dysplasia	3.9
Metabolic disease	2.0
Diaphragmatic hernia	2.0
Maternal morbidity	2.0
Cystic hygroma	2.0

OP-51

Giant cystic hygroma and EXIT procedure, case report

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A 30-year-old woman with a history of cesarean section was diagnosed with a cystic mass on the left side of the neck of the fetus during a detailed ultrasound examination at 20 weeks of gestation. The mass grew significantly by the 30th week, which led to close perinatal follow-up. At 38 weeks and 5 days, a cesarean section was performed using the EXIT procedure to safely control the newborn's airway. The 4200 gram baby was successfully intubated while still partially in utero. Postoperatively, the newborn underwent fine needle aspiration, removal of a cystic hygroma and bleomycin injection, resulting in a 50% reduction in mass size after sclerotherapy.

The EXIT (Extrauterine Intrapartum Treatment) procedure is used to treat fetuses at risk of airway obstruction at birth without interrupting blood flow through the umbilical cord. By maintaining the uteroplacental circulation, the procedure allows for safe intubation and treatment of the airway, reducing the risk of hypoxia, brain damage or death. Common indications include airway obstruction due to giant fetal neck masses, craniofacial syndromes and tumors. The EXIT procedure provides crucial time to secure the airway and prepare for surgery so that potentially fatal neonatal emergencies can be turned into controlled situations with better outcomes. It is a valuable technique for the treatment of prenatally diagnosed congenital malformations.

Keywords: Airway obstruction, EXIT procedure, giant cystic hygroma

Figure 1

Image of a giant cystic hygroma at 22 weeks

Figure 2

Image of a giant cystic hygroma at 30 weeks

Figure 3

Intubation during the EXIT procedure

Figure 4

Successfully intubated newborn after the EXIT procedure

OP-52

Follow up of pregnant women with sleep disorders in the first trimester in terms of adverse obstetric outcomes: A prospective cohort study

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AIM: This study investigated the relationship between sleep disorders in the first trimester of pregnancy and poor pregnancy outcomes like preeclampsia, preterm birth, intrauterine growth restriction, and gestational diabetes that can occur later in pregnancy.

METHODS: The study included 448 healthy, first-trimester pregnant women aged 18-45 who attended a high-risk pregnancy clinic in Ankara, Turkey in 2022. The women completed questionnaires to assess their sleep quality, daytime sleepiness, and chronotype. They were then monitored for the development of adverse obstetric outcomes.

RESULTS: 18.8% of the women had poor sleep quality and 14.8% had excessive daytime sleepiness. Chronotype assessment showed 5.6% were evening-type, 70% mixed-type, and 24.4% morning-type. During pregnancy, 0.9% developed preeclampsia, 6% had gestational diabetes, 6.3% threatened preterm labor, 0.9% had preterm premature rupture of membranes, 2.2% had intrauterine growth restriction, and 1.1% had gestational hypertension.

No significant associations were found between sleep quality/sleepiness and preeclampsia or gestational diabetes. However, women with excessive daytime sleepiness were more likely to experience fetal growth restriction. Moreover, the risk of threatened preterm labor was 2.59 times higher in women with sleep disorders compared to those without.

CONCLUSIONS: This study suggests a link between first-trimester sleep disturbances, particularly daytime sleepiness, and adverse pregnancy outcomes like fetal growth restriction and preterm labor. Larger studies are needed to further elucidate these relationships.

Keywords: Sleep Disorder, adverse obstetric outcome

OP-54

Distribution of Limb Anomalies Diagnosed in Prenatal Screening and Pregnancy Outcomes - Tertiary Centre Experience

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OBJECTIVE: Skeletal abnormalities may occur in isolation in a single organ or in association with comorbid anomalies. Considering relatively low incidence of such defects and related clinical problems, it is important to increase awareness among clinicians regarding prenatal diagnosis. For this purpose, we examined the distribution of limb anomalies, which constitute an important part of skeletal system anomalies, accompanying anomalies, prenatal diagnostic tests and pregnancy outcomes in last 2 years in our tertiary centre.

RESULTS: We retrospectively analysed data of 784 patients evaluated with abnormal ultrasound findings in our clinic. In total, 89 patients had skeletal dysplasias and 33 had limb abnormalities. Only lower extremity anomalies were observed in 14 patients, only upper extremity anomalies were observed in 13 patients and lower and upper extremity anomalies were observed together in 6 patients. Of 14 patients with isolated lower extremity anomalies, 7 were unilateral, 8 of 13 isolated upper extremity anomalies were unilateral, and in 6 patients with combined lower and upper extremity anomalies, anomalies were bilateral. Most common extremity anomalies were polydactyly (n:8) and club foot (n:6). The most common accompanying additional anomalies were skeletal dysplasias of other organs (n:9) and cardiac anomalies (n:8). The most common accompanying findings were single umbilical artery (n:8) and cleft palate (n:6). Chromosomal abnormalities were detected in 16 of 24 patients who underwent invasive prenatal diagnostic testing. Eight of these were trisomy 18. Total of 33 patients, 18 in termination, 12 in live birth and 3 resulted in stillbirth.

CONCLUSION: Difficulties are encountered in both prenatal counselling and optimum management of pregnancy in relatively rare anomalies. Therefore, multidisciplinary approach supporting prenatal diagnostic tests in addition to ultrasonographic fetal evaluation is required.

Keywords: Skeletal dysplasia, Limb anomalies, Prenatal diagnosis

OP-55

Outcomes of pregnant women and fetuses followed up with suspicion of sacrococcygeal teratoma

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INTRODUCTION: Sacrococcygeal teratoma (SCT) is the most common fetal neoplasm, with an incidence of 27,000/1. We aim to present the characteristics of pregnant women and fetuses who were followed up with suspicion of SCT in our hospital.

METHODS: We retrospectively analyzed data from 19 pregnant women and fetuses monitored for suspected fetal SCT at our hospital between 2014-2024. The histopathological results were categorized as mature, immature, or malignant, and further classified based on morphology as Types 1, 2, 3, and 4.

RESULTS: Lumbar lymphangioma, meningomyelocele and ovarian cyst were diagnosed and excluded in 3 fetuses with suspected SCT. Out of 16 pregnancies, 2 were terminated, 13 had caesarean sections, and 1 had a vaginal delivery. 42.8% of deliveries were term, and 57.2% were preterm, with an average gestational age of 34.4 weeks. 78.5% of the newborns were female. 21.5% of the newborns died due to perioperative bleeding. 72.7% of surviving neonates had mature teratomas, and 27.3% had immature teratomas. 20% of the children required reoperation due to recurrence (1 malignant yolk sac, 1 benign), and some had urinary and/or fecal incontinence (Table 1,2)(Figure1).

DISCUSSION: During pregnancy, patients with SCT need regular ultrasound checks to identify risks of preterm delivery, tumor rupture, and maternal mirror syndrome. Treatment planning and identifying fetuses at risk of fetal death due to hydrops are essential. Tumors can be successfully removed, but complications can affect quality of life. Both mature and immature teratomas can recur locally and at distant locations.

Keywords: sacrococcygeal teratoma

Figure 1

Table 1

Case	Age	Week	Type	First dimension	Last dimension	Placenta	AFI	Hearth findings	MCA-PSV (cm/s)	Additional anomaly
1	37	25	type2	56x51	153x90	N	N	120 midsystolic, cardiomegaly	1,68	UA blood flow loss
2	24	16	type1	22x27	79x39x41	N	Oligo	90 early systolic	1,3	
3	21	14	type2	30x28	130x94	N	Poly	100 midsystolic	0,99	
4	24	36	type2	54x26	55x27	N	N		0	0,9
5	26	33	type1	90x60	106x113	N	Poly		0	1
6	27	18	type2	26x23	107x120	N	N		0	1,2
7	21	28	type1	30x20	45x40	N	N		0	0,8
8	24	16	type2	12x20	250x100	N	N		0	1,3
9	25	23	type1	41x36	120x120	N	Poly		0	1,78
10	24	22	type3	35x20	100x80	N	Poly		0	1,2
11	24	23	type1	30x25	50x44	N	Poly		0	1
12	34	19	type2	35x34	200x150	ödemli	Poly	120 early systolic	1,62	
13	32	26	type4	97x70	130x120	N	Anhidro		0	1,5 multicystic dysplastic kidney
14	29	20	type3	70x60	130x100	N	Poly		0	1,7
15	34	24	type3	90x90	90x90	N	N		0	1,1 hydronephrosis
16	29	20	type2	43x34	125x100	N	Poly	150 early systolic	1,1	

AFI: amniotic fluid index, N: normally, Poly: polyhydramnios, Oligo: oligohydramnios, MCA-PSV: midcerebral artery peak systolic volume, UA: umbilical artery

Prenatal Characteristics

Table 2

Case	Delivery	Birth week	Sex	PP Hb	AFP	PP EKO	Operation (day)	Patology	Infant age	Walking	Urination	Defecation
1	Cs	35	F	15,8	1210	Heart failure symptoms		0 mature	1 N	N	N	N
2	Cs	37	F	17,9	41943	N		1 mature	1 N	N	N	N
3	Cs	28	F	14	60500	N		0 1.immature (gr1), 2.mature	3 N	Inkontinans	Inkontinans	
4	Cs	39	F	15,5	>20.000	N		3 mature	5 N	N	N	N
5	Cs	38	M	14,5	160548	N		5 immature (gr 2)	7 N	N	N	N
6	Cs	39	F	15,4	55266	N		1 1.matur, 2.yolc sac tumor (stage4)	6 N	Inkontinans	Inkontinans	
7	Vaginal	38	F	16	>20000	N		2 mature	9 N	N	N	N
8	Cs	36	F	16,1	>20000	N		1 mature	9 N	N	N	N
9	Cs	34	F	13,6	>20000	2.TR, 1.MR		0 mature	8 N	Inkontinans	N	N
10	Cs	38	F	17,5	>20000	N		3 immature (gr1)	9 N	N	N	Constipation
11	Cs	34	F	17,1	>80000	N		2 mature	?	U	Unreachable	U
12	Cs	28	M	13,6	.	EX	.	immature (gr3)	EX	.	.	.
13	Cs	32	M	0.	.	EX	.	.	0 EX	.	.	.
14	Cs	26	F	11,6	.	EX	.	.	0 EX	.	.	.
15	T(vaginal)	25	0	0.	.	T	.	.	0 T	.	.	.
16	T(Cs)	28	0	0.	.	T	.	.	0 T	.	.	.

Cs: cesarean section, AFP: alfa-feto protein, PP:postpartum, TR: tricuspid regurgitation, MR: mitral regurgitation, N: normally T: termination, gr:grade, U:unreachable

Postnatal Characteristics

OP-56

Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes in Triplet Pregnancies: A Retrospective Analysis

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OBJECTIVE: The aim of this study is to evaluate the maternal, fetal, and neonatal outcomes of 15 triplet pregnancies followed and delivered in our clinic. Triplet pregnancies are associated with increased maternal and neonatal complications, and understanding the outcomes can provide insight into optimal management strategies.

MATERIALS-METHODS: A retrospective analysis of 15 triplet pregnancies was performed. Data on maternal demographics (age, gravida, parity, BMI, comorbidities), pregnancy outcomes (delivery mode, gestational age, birth weight), and neonatal outcomes (Apgar scores, NICU admission, RDS, and other morbidities) were collected and analyzed.

RESULTS: The median maternal age was 30 years, and the majority of deliveries were by cesarean section (86.7%). The median birth weight was 1340 grams, with a median gestational age of 30 weeks. Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were 5 and 7, respectively. Most neonates required NICU admission (93.3%), with 75.6% diagnosed with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS). Additionally, 95.6% needed CPAP, and 73.3% required mechanical ventilation. Other complications included transient tachypnea of the newborn (91.1%), intraventricular hemorrhage (31.1%), and sepsis (31.1%) (Table).

CONCLUSION: Triplet pregnancies remain high-risk with significant maternal and neonatal morbidity. The high rates of preterm delivery and associated neonatal complications such as RDS and NICU admission highlight the importance of close monitoring and multidisciplinary care. Further studies are warranted to explore strategies to improve outcomes for both mothers and neonates in triplet pregnancies.

Keywords: Triplet pregnancy Neonatal outcomes Preterm delivery

Descriptive Statistics for Triplet Pregnancies

Variables	Median (Min-Max)
Maternal Age	30.0 (21-53)
Gravida	2 (1-4)
Parity	1 (1-3)
Living Children	3 (0-5)
BMI	29.4 (20.7-54.7)

Karyotype Analysis	6.7 (1)
Multifetal Reduction	6.7 (1)
MgSO4 Administration	66.7 (30)
Betamethasone Administration	100 (15)
Neonatal Birth Weight (grams)	1340 (390-2350)
Gestational Age (weeks)	30 (22-34)
Apgar 1	5 (2-8)
Apgar 5	7 (3-9)
Fetal Hematocrit (%)	51.6 (43.4-62.8)
CS	86.7 (39)
FGR	28.9 (13)
PPROM	33.3 (15)
Neonatal Hypoglycemia	26.7 (12)
TTN	91.1 (41)
RDS	75.6 (34)
CPAP	95.6 (43)
Mechanical Ventilation	73.3 (33)
Phototherapy	33.3 (15)
IVH	31.1 (14)
NEC	6.7 (3)
Neonatal Sepsis	31.1 (14)
Surfactant Administration	66.7 (30)
Seizures	8.9 (49)

BMI: Body Mass Index, CS: Cesarean Section, FGR: Fetal Growth Restriction, PPRM: Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes, TTN: Transient Tachypnea of the Newborn, RDS: Respiratory Distress Syndrome, CPAP: Continuous Positive Airway Pressure, IVH: Intraventricular Hemorrhage, NEC: Necrotizing Enterocolitis. In the statistical summary presented in the table, "median (min-max)" is used for continuous variables, while "percentage (%) and number (n)" are used for categorical variables.

OP-57

Does foramen ovale restriction matter in the intrauterine period?

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AIM: To emphasize the importance of restriction (rFO) or premature closure (cFO) of the foramen ovale in the fetus without congenital heart disease.

METHOD: During the follow-up of the patient who applied to the Perinatology Department of Izmir City Hospital, it was determined that the foramen ovale (FO) flap was aneurysmatic in the ultrasonography. The diagnosis of rFO was made according to previously published criteria: (1) FO diameter < 2.5 mm, (2) FO right to left Doppler > 40 cm/s, (3) FO/right atrial diameter < 0.3, and (4) FO/outgoing aortic diameter < 0.52.

RESULTS: A 31-year-old, G5P4 patient was referred to our outpatient clinic at the 34th week of gestation with a preliminary diagnosis of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). In the ultrasonographic scan, fetal growth restriction was observed. In the fetal echocardiographic examination, the right atrium was wide in the 4-chamber view, the FO flap was aneurysmatic, and the aorta was narrower than normal in the 3-vessel-trachea view. FO diameter was measured as 2.1 mm (Figure 1). FO right to left Doppler was > 60 cm/s. No cardiac decompensation developed during follow-up. The patient had delivery at the 37th week with the diagnosis of IUGR. No problems were encountered in the postnatal follow-ups.

CONCLUSION: Premature closure of the fetal FO may lead to failure of the left ventricle development, enlargement of the right heart structures, hydrops, and even intrauterine death. If birth occurs before irreversible structural abnormalities or major complications develop, the prognosis is good after birth.

Keywords: Foramen ovale; fetal echocardiography; Doppler ultrasound

Figure 1

Ultrasound findings of the fetus who had restrictive foramen ovale (LA, left atrium; RA, right atrium; LV, left ventricle; RV, right ventricle; FO, foramen ovale)

OP-58

Postpartum Hemolytic Uremic Syndrome

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INTRODUCTION: Pregnancy-associated thrombotic microangiopathies (TMAs), such as hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) and thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP), are rare with an incidence of 1:25,000 births. They are obstetric emergencies requiring prompt diagnosis and treatment to improve outcomes. TMAs are characterized by microangiopathic hemolytic anemia and organ dysfunction, affecting the brain, kidneys, heart, liver, lungs, and skin. Atypical HUS (aHUS), driven by complement system dysregulation, can be triggered by pregnancy, systemic lupus erythematosus, or malignant hypertension.

CASE: We present a case of a 38-year-old woman who developed aHUS postpartum after an emergency cesarean due to HELLP. She was referred with thrombocytopenia, and her peripheral blood smear showed schistocytes, indicating microangiopathic hemolytic anemia. Despite seven sessions of plasmapheresis and hemodialysis, the patient was resistant and was diagnosed with aHUS based on ADAMTS13. Eculizumab treatment was initiated, leading to improvement in renal function. A renal biopsy was planned.

In conclusion, life-threatening syndromes like TTP, HELLP, and postpartum HUS should be included in the differential diagnosis of thrombocytopenia and hemolytic anemia during pregnancy. While the pathogenesis varies, they present similarly, and empirical treatment must be started promptly. Our case emphasizes that early diagnosis and treatment of pregnancy-related TMAs are critical for saving lives.

Keywords: Postpartum HUS, TTP, HELLP

OP-59

Limb Body Wall Complex: A Case Series of a Rare Anomaly

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OBJECTIVE: Limb body wall complex (LBWC) is a rare and complicated syndrome characterized by a wide spectrum of severe abnormalities of the body wall. The incidence at birth is 0.32 per 100,000 births. Since the prognosis for foetuses with LBWC is poor and fatal, the diagnosis is crucial. We report three cases diagnosed in our clinic.

METHOD: A presentation of three LBWC cases evaluated in our clinic, accompanied by a literature review.

FINDINGS: LBWC was diagnosed in a total of 3 cases in our clinic. The first patient was referred for an oligohydramnios and the other two patients for an abdominal wall defect. Our first case was a 23-year-old G3P0 with gestational age of 15 weeks. Ultrasound examination revealed omphalocele, meningomyelocele in the sacral region and anomaly of the lower extremities. The fetus was attached to the placenta at the site of omphalocele. Second case was a 30-year-old, primigravida patient with a gestational age of 12 weeks. An omphalocele and absence of the right lower limb were noted. Third case was 23-year-old, primigravida and 12 weeks pregnant. An omphalocele, polydactyly of the left foot and a short umbilical cord were observed. All three patients were diagnosed with LBWC and offered termination. The first patient accepted termination while the others refused.

CONCLUSION: Although the pathogenesis of LBWC is still controversial, it must be differentiated from gastroschisis and omphalocele. The diagnosis can be made with ultrasonography from the first trimester. Medical termination after early diagnosis is recommended treatment.

Keywords: Limb body wall complex, Omphalocele

Abdominal wall defect with attached placent

Abdominal wall defect with attached plasenta

LBWC, Absence of the lower limb

LBWC, Absence of the lower limb

LBWC, Anomaly of the lower extremities

LBWC, Anomaly of the lower extremities

LBWC, Myelomeningocele

LBWC, Myelomeningocele

OP-60

Post-laser Twin Anemia Polycythemia Sequence: A Case Report

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INTRODUCTION: Twin anemia polycythemia sequence (TAPS) is a consequence of unequal sharing of red blood cells between monochorionic twins resulting in anemia in the donor and polycythemia in the recipient. TAPS is estimated approximately 2-13% post-laser.

CASE: Age 34, gravid 3, monochorionic twin pregnant was referred our clinic in 21st week with pre-diagnosis twin-twin transfusion syndrome (TTTS). Fetoscopic laser photocoagulation (FLF) planned for the patient evaluated Quintero stage 2 TTTS as a result of her first examination. Amniotic cavity of fetus was introduced by 10F trocar under spinal anesthesia on 21 weeks and 5th day. The ablation of anastomoses in anterior placenta was done by FLF using 30 watt energy (Figure 1). 214 seconds and 5781 joule energy was used in total during operation taking approximately 30 minutes. Amniotic fluid and doppler parameters of both fetuses were at normal limits until post-laser second week. Middle cerebral artery (MCA) peak systolic velocity (PSV) increment of recipient fetus appearing post-laser second week was consistent with fetal anemia. As donor's MCA PSV was 2.53 Mom and recipient's 0.57 Mom, caesarean decision was made when 29 weeks 6 days. Fetuses were given birth with the scores of 6/8 APGAR, recipient 1530gr and donor 1350gr. Hemoglobin levels were recipient 11,2g/dl, donor 21,7g/dL. The recipient was pale but the donor plethoric (Figure 2). Both didn't need transfusion in postnatal period.

CONCLUSION: For TAPS, it's important to evaluate post-laser cases that are effective treatment on TTTS cases Quintero stage 2 and above.

Keywords: Twin-anemia polycythemia sequence, post-laser TAPS, fetal anemia

Figure 1

Image of painted placenta

Figure 2

Postnatal images: donor plethoric and recipient pale

OP-61

Comparison of birth outcomes of pregnant women with lateral placenta with other locations of placenta: A prospective cohort study

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OBJECTIVE: To compare neonatal intensive care needs based on placental location (lateral vs. anterior, posterior, and fundus) and discuss potential changes in pregnancy follow-up and delivery practices.

METHODS: This prospective cohort study included single pregnancies of women aged 18-45 years, with gestational age ≥ 37 weeks, and no additional diseases. Pregnancies with IUGR, placental adhesion anomalies, multiple gestations, or fetal death were excluded. Placental locations were recorded as anterior, posterior, lateral, or fundus.

RESULTS: Of 502 pregnancies, placental locations were: anterior (44.6%), posterior (29.9%), lateral (16.9%), and fundus (8.6%). No statistically significant differences were found in baby weight, first-minute Apgar scores or neonatal intensive care needs across placental locations. Mothers with anterior placental location had significantly lower mean BMI (24.98 ± 3.53 kg/m²), age (26.79 ± 4.60 years), and gestational age (38.72 ± 1.21 weeks) compared to other locations ($p < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION: No significant relationship was found between lateral placental location and newborn outcomes. However, mothers with anterior placental location had lower mean gestational age, age, and BMI compared to other locations. Further studies with increased data diversity are recommended to guide future research in this area.

Keywords: Lateral placenta, newborn, pregnancy

OP-62

Awareness and attitudes of pregnant women about prenatal screening and diagnostic tests

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AIM: To investigate the awareness and attitudes regarding prenatal screening and diagnostic tests

METHOD: A total of 259 pregnancies were enrolled in our study. The study investigated the association between the option to undertake screening and diagnostic tests by analyzing sociodemographic and obstetric factors through a series of questions. The participants were categorized into groups and were presented with 5-point Likert-type questions to evaluate their understanding of screening and diagnostic tests (Figure 1). Based on the responses provided by the participants, each question was evaluated individually and scored.

RESULTS: The rate of having prenatal screening test was and prenatal diagnosis test in the recommended group was 52.1 and 44.8% respectively (Table 1-2). Employed pregnant women exhibited a greater rate of screening tests compared to unemployed pregnant women, whereas those with consanguineous marriages showed a higher rate of screening tests compared to those without (Table 1). It was shown that the questionnaire scores of participants who both did and did not undergo a screening test were significantly higher among those who graduated from university or above (Table 3). The incidence of undergoing the tests was found to be higher among those who were advised to perform prenatal diagnostic testing before to the 20th week of pregnancy. The rate of prenatal diagnostic testing was recorded as higher in employed participants than in unemployed participants (Table 4).

CONCLUSION: Informing pregnancies about prenatal screening and diagnostic tests are crucial, and enhanced awareness can be attained through the establishment of a well-organized network.

Keywords: Prenatal diagnosis, prenatal care, prenatal screening tests

Figure 1

Distribution of participants

OP-63

Association Between Umbilical Cord Blood Gas Values And Mode Of Delivery In Cases Of Preeclampsia

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Preeclampsia is a serious pregnancy complication characterized by high blood pressure and proteinuria, typically emerging in the third trimester. This study aimed to evaluate the relationship between the mode of delivery and fetal well-being, specifically through fetal cord blood gas values. We analyzed data from 96 patients who delivered due to preeclampsia at Ankara Etlik City Hospital from January to August 2024. Blood gas parameters, including pH, lactate, and base deficit, were assessed. Results indicated no significant difference in pH values between vaginal delivery (7.13 ± 0.13) and caesarean section (7.14 ± 0.17) ($p=0.97$). However, significant differences were noted in base deficit (-4.34 ± 0.50 for vaginal delivery vs. -4.03 ± 0.72 for caesarean section, $p=0.015$) and lactate levels (3.51 ± 0.57 for vaginal delivery vs. 3.01 ± 0.87 for caesarean section, $p=0.001$). The findings suggest that while vaginal delivery may be suitable for stable patients, caesarean sections may better support fetal well-being in cases of preeclampsia.

Keywords: blood gas values, mode of delivery, preeclampsia

Blood gas values according to mode of delivery

	Vaginal Delivery (n:48)	Caesarean section (n:48)	P Value
pH	7.13 ± 0.13	7.14 ± 0.17	0.97
Base deficit value	-4.34 ± 0.50	-4.03 ± 0.72	0.015
Lactate value	3.51 ± 0.57	3.01 ± 0.87	0.001

OP-64

Budd Chiari syndrome presenting with abdominal wall varices in pregnancy: a case report

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BACKGROUND:

Budd-Chiari syndrome (BCS) is an uncommon condition characterized by obstruction of the hepatic venous outflow tract.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 29-year-old, 25-week pregnant woman with her first pregnancy was referred to our clinic with a preliminary diagnosis of immune thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP). The patient's laboratory findings showed impaired liver parameters such as pancytopenia, elevated alanine transaminase, aspartate aminotransferase, bilirubin and low fibrinogen, albumin. When ultrasound and MRI findings were examined, there were splenomegaly and findings in favor of portal hypertension, and the liver was observed to be cirrhotic. 2.5 cm vascular collateral structures continuing in the superior part of the uterus adjacent to the umbilicus were observed. (Figure 1) Endoscopy was planned at the 26th week of pregnancy and band ligation was applied to the esophageal varices seen during the operation. The patient was taken to cesarean section at the 28th week with the indication of breech presentation during labor. The collaterals mentioned in the ultrasound were observed during the cesarean section. (Figure 2) Postpartum hysterectomy was performed due to atony. During the intensive care follow-ups after c/s, the patient was started on aldactone treatment due to widespread ascites in the abdomen. The patient was discharged with a stable condition.

CONCLUSION: The presence of coagulopathy, portal hypertension and gastrointestinal varices due to liver dysfunction increases the risk of life-threatening bleeding in pregnant women.

Keywords: portal hypertension, cirrhosis, pancytopenia

Figure 1

Ultrasound image of maternal abdominal wall varices located on the superior part of the uterus.

Figure 2

Intraoperative image of the maternal abdominal wall varices

E-POSTERS

EP-34

Perinatal Outcome in Pregnancy With Cardiac Disease

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Hemodynamic changes in maternal physiology during pregnancy may cause differences in the perinatal outcome of pregnant women with cardiac disease. Fetal complications may vary according to the type and severity of the disease. Congenital heart disease, valvular heart disease complicated acute rheumatic fever and hypertension-related complications constitute the major part of cardiac diseases.

To assess the perinatal outcome a descriptive study was conducted among 120 pregnant women with cardiac disease admitted to Gazi University Department of Perinatology between January 2018 and December 2023. Congenital heart disease was present 41.2% valvular disease was 26.1%, arrhythmia was 13.4%, hypertensive disorders was 11.8%, and other was 7.6%. The mean gestational age at birth was 36.73 weeks (SD = 2.74) and the median value was 37 weeks, according to the results of post-hoc analysis, there were significant differences between congenital heart disease and the other groups ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that infants of mothers with congenital heart disease were more complicated with prematurity. The mean weight of infants in the congenital heart disease group was 2,581. grams (SD = 968.8), the lowest mean weight among all groups. Results indicate that birth weights of infants of mothers with congenital heart disease were lower than the other groups ($p < 0.05$). At that point preconceptional counseling especially those with congenital heart disease, is important. If necessary, corrective surgical and interventional procedures should be done before pregnancy and pregnancy should be started under optimum conditions. Perinatal outcome can be improved by team approach at tertiary care centre.

Keywords: Pregnancy, cardiac disease, perinatal outcome

figure 1

		Hastalık Grubu										Ki Kare Testi	
		Aritmi		Kapak Hastalığı		Hipertansif Hastalıklar		Konjenital Kalp Hastalığı		Diğer			
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	X2	p
Ağırlık (gr)	Düşük doğum ağırlığı	0	0,0	5	16,1	3	21,4	19	38,8	4	44,4	13,929	0,005
	Normal doğum ağırlığı	16	100,0	26	83,9	11	78,6	30	61,2	5	55,6		
Doğum Haftası (Hafta)	34 hafta ve altı	0	0,0	1	3,2	3	21,4	11	22,4	0	0,0	35,380	0,000
	34-37 hafta	1	6,3	11	35,5	5	35,7	27	55,1	7	77,8		
	38-42 hafta	15	93,8	19	61,3	6	42,9	11	22,4	2	22,2		

Table 3 contains the chi-square test results showing the distribution of infants' birth weight and gestational age

figure 2

	Hastalık Grubu															Kruskal Wallis Testi		Post Hoc
	1-Aritmi			2-Kapak Hastalığı			3-Hipertansif Hastalıklar			4-Konjenital Kalp Hastalığı			5-Diğer			X ²	p	
	X	ss.	M	X	ss.	M	X	ss.	M	X	ss.	M	X	ss.	M			
Yaşı (Takip)	30,25	4,54	30,00	30,26	5,38	31,00	30,00	6,68	29,00	30,61	5,17	31,00	31,00	6,48	32,00	0,633	0,959	-
Yaşı (Doğum)	30,44	4,38	30,00	30,39	5,41	31,00	30,14	6,67	30,00	30,80	5,22	31,00	31,44	6,44	32,00	0,655	0,957	-
Ağırlık (gr)	3.253,4	257,1	3.215,0	3.173,3	618,5	3.280,0	2.881,0	667,3	2.967,5	2.581,6	968,8	2.712,5	2.738,8	522,1	2.720,0	16,18	0,00	1-4
Boy (cm)	49,59	1,85	50,00	47,48	4,39	49,00	46,89	4,68	48,50	44,49	6,78	47,00	46,61	2,57	46,00	17,84	0,00	1-5
Baş Çevresi (cm)	35,28	1,66	35,00	34,97	3,79	35,00	34,46	1,60	35,00	32,48	4,10	34,00	33,72	1,64	33,00	10,05	0,04	1-4
Doğum Haftası (Hafta)	38,44	1,03	39,00	37,81	1,76	38,00	36,50	2,71	37,00	35,51	3,24	37,00	37,00	1,58	37,00	27,94	0,00	1-3
																2	0	1-4
																		2-4

Table 2 shows the results of Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney post-hoc analyses with Bonferroni corrected Mann-Whitney test for the variables age, weight, height, head circumference and gestational age

EP-35

Prevalence And Affecting Risk Factors Of Postpartum Depression(PPD): Our Data

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INTRODUCTION: Postpartum depression (PPD) is a pathology which has short and long-term effects on mothers, their children and families. The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of PPD at UHOG "Koço Gliozheni" and its risk factors.

METHODOLOGY: This is a prospective study conducted from May 2021 to May 2022. 256 women who delivered a live child and gave consent, were enrolled. Patients with a history of psychiatric problems were excluded. Patients were contacted 6 weeks after delivery and evaluated by means of EPDS for the presence of PPD. 199 women met the inclusion criteria. Mode of delivery, age, education, living area and unemployment were explored as possible causes. Statistical analysis was performed by simple odd ratio and chi-square. Significance was set as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS: The prevalence of PPD was calculated to be 8%, 16 women manifested a degree of PPD. 6 (37.5%) women had minimal depression, 4 (25%) had mild depression, 3 (18.75%) had moderate depression, 2 (12.5%) had moderately to severe depression, and 1 (6.25%) had severe depression. Adolescents had an 8-fold risk of developing depression (OR 8.57, CI 1.3 - 55.6, $p = 0.02$). C-section (OR 1.39, CI 1.46 - 4.19, $p = 0.05$), education (OR 2.01, CI 0.69 - 5.8, $p = 0.19$), living area (OR 1.12, CI 0.34 - 3.66, $p = 0.84$) and unemployment (OR 1.44, CI 0.5 - 4.14, $p = 0.49$) were not linked to higher rates of manifesting PPD.

CONCLUSIONS: PPD affects the quality of life of new mothers. Early recognition and treatment are crucial for the overall family wellbeing.

Keywords: PPD, Prevalence, Risk-factors

Chart of the Cases

Chart of Women who manifested a degree of PPD

EP-36

Obstetrical Challenges In The Presence Of Advanced Fetal Weight

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INTRODUCTION: Macrosomia is strongly associated with adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. The effectiveness of screening remains controversial because expecting a macrosomic fetus affects intrapartum management, promoting elective cesarean sections. This study aims to identify differences in outcomes and management among cases with predicted and unpredicted macrosomia.

MATERIALS-METHODS: This is a retrospective study of 896 live-born, cephalic, singleton macrosomic babies delivered from January 2017 to December 2021. Cases of macrosomia were categorized as unpredicted and predicted. Ultrasonographic weight predictions are made using the Hadlock formula. Data regarding mode of delivery, shoulder dystocia, perineal trauma, episiotomy use, and postpartum hemorrhage were retrieved. Data were stored in a secure database. The review board of the institution approved the study. Statistical analysis is performed utilizing the Mann-Whitney U test for continuous data, the chi-square test for cardinal variables, and logistic regression analysis. Significance was set as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS: Macrosomia is successfully predicted in 308 (34.4%) women. The rate of cesarean sections was significantly higher in the predicted group (46.4% vs. 35.4%, $p=0.002$). The higher rate of elective cesarean sections among women with predicted macrosomia (26.1% vs. 15.1%, $p=0.02$) contributed to this difference. Women with predicted macrosomic fetuses were more prone to perineal traumas, such as episiotomy (48.9% vs. 31.3%) or third/4th -degree lacerations (4.8% vs. 1.95%). Shoulder dystocia and other neonatal complications did not differ significantly among the groups.

CONCLUSION: Acknowledging macrosomia before delivery increases elective cesarean sections and it decreases the rate of adverse neonatal outcomes such as birth asphyxia.

Keywords: Macrosomia, C-section, outcomes

Tables of Results

Table 1. Baseline characteristics

Characteristics	Macrosomia n=351	Normal birth weight n=3058	p
Age (years)	30.1 +/- 5.17	28.9 +/- 8.4	<0.05
BMI	29.2 +/- 3.54	26.1 +/- 2.78	<0.05
Weight gain >12.5 kg	240 (68.37%)	1642 (53.7%)	<0.001
Primiparous	136 (38.74%)	1403 (45.9%)	0.01
Gestational Diabetes	9 (2.56%)	64 (2.1%)	0.56
Gestational age at delivery	40.4 +/- 2.17	39.5 +/- 2.23	<0.05

Table 2. Maternal and neonatal outcomes

Outcomes	Macrosomia n=351	Normal birth weight n=3058	p
Vaginal Birth	213 (60.7%)	2149 (70.3%)	0.002
Cesarean Section	138 (39.3%)	909 (29.7%)	
Elective C/S	66 (18.8%)	785 (25.67%)	<0.001
Emergency C/S	72 (20.5%)	124 (13.6%)	
Episiotomy	142 (40.45%)	978 (31.9%)	0.001
Laceration	11 (3.13%)	44 (1.44%)	0.02
Forceps	3 (0.85%)	0	0.006
PPH	18 (5.12%)	110 (3.6%)	0.15
Shoulder Dystocia	17 (4.84%)	33 (1.07%)	<0.001

EP-37

Maternal Outcome of Severe Preeclampsia: Data From A University Hospital Setting In Tirana, Albania

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INTRODUCTION: Preeclampsia is a hypertensive multisystem disorder of pregnancy that complicates up to 10% of pregnancies worldwide and is one of the leading causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. This study aims to evaluate maternal complications associated with severe preeclampsia.

MATERIALS-METHODS: This is a retrospective cross-sectional study conducted in the UHOG "Koço Gliozheni", in Tirana. Primary outcomes evaluated: maternal death, eclampsia, stroke, HELLP syndrome, and pulmonary edema. Secondary outcomes: renal failure, admission in ICU, caesarean section, placental abruption, and postpartum hemorrhage. Fisher's exact test and Chi-squared test were used as statistical methods.

RESULTS: In women with severe preeclampsia we found higher rates of complications comparing to the group with preeclampsia. Eclampsia (1.5% vs. 7.1%, $P < 0.001$), HELLP syndrome (2.4% vs. 11.0%; $P < 0.001$), stroke (0.5% vs 1.9%, $P = 0.105$) pulmonary edema (0.25% vs. 1.3%, $P = 0.0035$), renal failure (0.9% vs. 2.6%, $P = 0.107$), admission in ICU (19.5% vs. 71.4%, $P = 0.007$), caesarean section rates (55.5% vs. 77%, $P = 0.508$), placental abruption (4.3% vs. 7.8%, $P = 0.103$) and severe postpartum hemorrhage (3.2% vs. 3.9%, $P = 0.628$).

CONCLUSION: Severe preeclampsia is associated with high rates of maternal severe morbidity and early diagnosis and timely intervention can prevent life treating complications.

Keywords: HELLP-syndrome; maternal outcome; pulmonary-edema;

Rates of complications report

EP-38

Overview of healthcare-associated infections in newborns: epidemiological data and prevention issues

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INTRODUCTION: Nosocomial infections pose a major challenge in newborns, especially in preterm and newborns requiring prolonged hospitalization due to complications. This study aims to assess the hospital prevalence of hospital-acquired nosocomial infections, identify the main risk factors in newborns, and determine the microbial species responsible.

METHODOLOGY: A retrospective study was conducted on newborns hospitalized for more than 48 hours at the neonatology of the specialized maternity and childhood hospital in Oran, over a period of three months, from 1 October 2022 to 31 December. Inclusion criteria were defined based on length of hospital stay and invasive procedures such as peripheral venous catheters and force-feeding.

RESULTS: The results indicate that factors such as age at the time of hospitalization in the first days of life, duration of hospitalization and use of invasive procedures are significant risk factors. The nosocomial infections analyzed were mainly of bacterial origin, with a predominance of Gram-positive Bacilli, *Escherichia coli* being the most common pathogen, closely followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Digestive infection was identified as the most common localization among the cases studied, followed by sepsis and urinary tract infections.

DISCUSSION The findings highlight the importance of increased awareness and implementation of a strategy based on monitoring and adherence to good hygiene practices. This aims to reduce the cross-transmission of multidrug-resistant germs, helping to improve protocols for preventing nosocomial infections in newborns.

CONCLUSION This study provides significant insight into the prevalence of nosocomial infections in newborns, highlighting key risk factors and the pathogens most frequently involved.

Keywords: Nosocomial infection, germ, Antibiotic resistance

EP-40

A Case of Prenatally Diagnosed Schizencephaly

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INTRODUCTION: According to prior research, the incidence of schizencephaly is 1.54 per 100,000 live births, with the majority of cases detected after birth. It is thought to be a damaging process of the fetal brain caused by vascular damage. Fetal schizencephaly clefts can extend from the ventricles to the pial surface via the hemispheres. The most prevalent kinds of fetal schizencephaly are clefts that are touching (closed lip) or widely spaced (open lip). Because the prognosis is often poor, antenatal ultrasound (US) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are critical in the diagnosis of this condition, as well as in prenatal consultation and therapy.

CASE: 38 weeks G3P2 patient was admitted to the delivery room due to unreliable NST; upon detection of developmental delay in the sonography, we were consulted. Schizencephaly was regarded in the foreground when sonography revealed a hypoechoic wedge-shaped region in the fetal cerebral hemisphere. Upon fetal measurements consistent with 33 weeks, EFW, and AC < 1% percentile; growth restriction was diagnosed. Fetal MRI revealed open lip schizencephaly associated with the left lateral ventricle at the level of the left parietal lobe vertex, as well as increased surrounding cortex thickness. A 2110 gr girl baby was delivered by cesarean section. There was no feature in the TORCH panel.

CONCLUSION: The prognosis of schizencephaly is related to the extent of the lesion. Schizencephaly can cause motor retardation, mental retardation, seizures and developmental delay. Prenatal diagnosis of schizencephaly is important for prenatal management and consultation.

Keywords: Schizencephaly

Figure 1

Fetal head ultrasound at 38 weeks gestation

Figure 2

Fetal magnetic resonance imaging

EP-41

A Case of 7q32 Microdeletion with Coincidence Prenatal Diagnosis

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INTRODUCTION: Long arm microdeletion of chromosome 7 is uncommon. Microcephaly, ear abnormalities, a broad nasal tip, prominent forehead, cleft lip and palate, and genital anomalies are common characteristics. In addition, postnatal growth retardation and hypotonia are prevalent.

CASE: A 32-year-old G2 P1 patient with a first-degree consanguineous marriage was referred to our perinatology clinic due to a biochemical risk of 1:341. USG revealed a fetus with no evident congenital abnormalities and a gestational age of 17 weeks. The patient underwent amniocentesis at the mother's request. The karyotype was identified as 46XX der (7) del (7)q32. In the 24th week of pregnancy, BPD and HC measures were determined as microcephaly below the 1% percentile. Fetocide was carried out with the family's permission. A deceased fetus weighing 610 grams was delivered.

CONCLUSION: Patients with 7q- have only a few common characteristics, including mental and growth retardation and microcephaly. Hopefully, as additional 7q- patients are uncovered, a more detailed clinical description of this aberration will become possible. Amniocentesis and karyotype analysis are extremely significant in consanguineous pregnancies. This will provide families the choice of terminating their pregnancy if unusual defects are identified.

Keywords: 7q32 Microdeletion

Figure 1.

EP-42

Intrauterine Diagnosis of Rhombencephalosynapsis

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INTRODUCTION: Rhombencephalosynapsis (RES) is a rare noncystic posterior fossa anomaly. This malformation is characterized by agenesis of the vermis and fusion of the cerebellar hemispheres, peduncles, and dentate nuclei. Ultrasonographically, on axial transcerebellar section, the vermis is absent and the hypoplastic cerebellar hemispheres are fused in the midline. RES patients may show clinical signs of delayed brain development, epilepsy, spasticity, hypotonia, or hydrocephalus. Only 65 cases have been detected in the fetal stage, according to the literature.

CASE: A 27-year-old G1P0 patient who was 23 weeks pregnant came to us for a routine checkup. The patient's fetal ultrasound revealed the following: Cerebellum: 22+1 weeks 55% percentile (atypical look) and Lateral ventricle: 12 mm. Amniocentesis, chromosomal karyotyping, microarray, and Whole Exom Sequencing were conducted, and a fetal MRI was scheduled for the 27th week of pregnancy. In the patient's control sonography, the fetal MRI revealed rhombencephalosynapsis, and the lateral ventricle size indicated significant ventriculomegaly. The family was advised of the terrible prognosis, and the pregnancy was terminated.

CONCLUSION: In this example, the value of a thorough neurosonography evaluation is once again demonstrated. In cases of doubt, we appreciate the importance of fetal MRI and its role in diagnosis. In this patient, because the cerebellar vermis was not visible and had an abnormal morphology, we were able to make the diagnosis by analyzing the posterior fossa with MRI.

Keywords: Rhombencephalosynapsis

Figure 1.

Prenatal sonography of the posterior fossa shows unusual appearance of the cerebellar vermis.

EP-43

Placenta accreta spectrum in dichorionic diamniotic twin pregnancy: a case report

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INTRODUCTION: Placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) encompasses abnormal placental invasions, including placenta accreta, increta, and percreta. These conditions are strongly associated with prior uterine surgery, such as cesarean sections. In twin pregnancies, the presence of multiple placentas further complicates the diagnosis and management of PAS, necessitating early detection and multidisciplinary care.

CASE: A 38-year-old (G4P3), with a history of three previous cesarean sections, presented with a dichorionic diamniotic twin pregnancy. At 22 weeks of gestation, she was referred to perinatology due to total placenta previa. Ultrasound examination revealed total placenta previa and a lacunar appearance in the right placenta, along with hypervascular areas near the bladder and loss of the hypoechoic zone, leading to the assessment of placenta accreta. The placenta of the left twin was located on the left lateral uterine wall. The right fetus, affected by placenta percreta, also showed selective fetal growth restriction (sFGR) type 1. Weekly Doppler studies were conducted, and a cesarean section was performed at 35 weeks due to reduced fetal movements and positive tocometer findings.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION: This case emphasizes the complexities of managing placenta accreta spectrum in a patient with multiple prior cesarean sections. In twin pregnancies, the risk of PAS increases, particularly with the presence of multiple placentas. Early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management are crucial to minimizing maternal and fetal risks. Clinicians should maintain a high level of vigilance in such cases to improve perinatal outcomes.

Keywords: Placenta accreta spectrum, placenta previa, twin pregnancy

placenta accreta in twin pregnancies

placenta accreta in twin pregnancies

uterus plasenta accreta

post op uterus after hysterectomy

EP-44

Pentalogy of Cantrell in Monochorionic Monoamniotic Twin Pregnancy

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INTRODUCTION: Pentalogy of Cantrell is a rare birth defect that occurs once in 200,000 births. It is characterized by five main features: diaphragm, abdominal wall, sternal, pericardial defects and cardiac abnormalities. We report a case of this very rare pathology, which is even rarer with early prenatal diagnosis.

CASE: A 10-week 2-day G1P0 patient applied to us for routine control, and sonography showed a monochorionic monoamniotic twin pregnancy compatible with 10 weeks. In one of the fetuses, the fetal heart was visualized through a defect located in the lower sternum, outside the rib cage, along with anterior diaphragmatic and ventral abdominal wall defects suggestive of thoracoabdominal ectopia cordis. At the base of the umbilical cord insertion, there was a membrane-covered, midline abdominal wall defect containing herniated abdominal organs including the liver and ectopic cardia. Nuchal translucency was 4.5 mm. The other fetus had megacystis and omphalocele. Nuchal translucency was 7 mm. The family was informed of the poor prognosis and the pregnancy was terminated.

CONCLUSION: Pentalogy of Cantrell is a very rare congenital condition. Early diagnosis is possible in the first trimester. Early recognition of pentalogy of Cantrell is crucial for prompt and appropriate management.

Keywords: Pentalogy of Cantrell

Figure 1.

Two-dimensional sonographic examination showed that the heart (black arrow) and liver extruded through the lower chest and upper abdomen.

EP-46

Megacystis-microcolon-intestinal hypoperistalsis syndrome: case report and review of prenatal ultrasonographic findings

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INTRODUCTION: MMIHS is a congenital disease characterized by bladder distension and gastrointestinal hypoperistalsis, with an unknown etiology and no mechanical obstruction. Although its prevalence is not well established, literature indicates that 230 patients have been diagnosed, 71% of whom are female fetuses, similar to our case. We aim to share a case of MMIHS diagnosed prenatally.

CASE PRESENTATION: A 25-year-old woman, G1P0, presented at 35 weeks of gestation with a preliminary diagnosis of preterm labor. Her medical history was unremarkable, and combined screening results indicated low risk; however, a detailed ultrasound had not been performed. The ultrasound findings showed a fetal bladder anteroposterior diameter of 34.5 mm and a transverse diameter of 26.2 mm, with a bladder wall thickness of 2.1 mm. The bowel loop measured 36.8 mm in length and 11.6 mm in diameter, filled with meconium. The deepest single pocket of amniotic fluid measured 10.1 cm, and the kidneys and ureters appeared normal. The patient was monitored at 45-minute intervals, with continued bladder dilation observed. Cordocentesis information was provided, but the patient declined the procedure. She remains under observation in our clinic.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION: MMIHS should be considered when prenatal ultrasound shows a significantly enlarged bladder and normal or increased amniotic fluid, with or without hydronephrosis. Polyhydramnios, normal bladder wall thickness, and higher prevalence in female fetuses are crucial indicators for differentiating MMIHS from other lower urinary tract obstructions.

Keywords: Megacystis-microcolon-intestinal hypoperistalsis, polyhydramnios, prenatal diagnosis

amniotic fluid

Deepest single pocket of amniotic fluid measured 10.1 cm

bladder

fetal bladder anteroposterior diameter of 34.5 mm and a transverse diameter of 26.2 mm

bowel loop

Bowel loop measured 36.8 mm in length and 11.6 mm in diameter, filled with meconium

EP-47

Intrauterine Diagnosis of Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia: A Case Report

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INTRODUCTION: Congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) is a rare developmental defect of the diaphragm that causes herniation of abdominal organs into the chest cavity. Neonates with CDH often experience mild to severe respiratory distress within the first few hours of life, leading to significant morbidity and mortality risks.

CASE PRESENTATION: A 35-week nulliparous woman was referred for diaphragmatic hernia and short humerus/femur length. In our perinatology policlinic, polyhydramnios was observed, and abdominal diameter and femur length measurements were below the 1st percentile. Anatomical examination showed the fetal heart displaced rightward due to a left-sided hernia, with the stomach, intestines, and left liver lobe herniated into the thorax. The median observed/expected lung-to-head ratio (O/E LHR) was 22%. The patient delivered via cesarean section at 36 weeks due to preterm rupture of membranes. The newborn was intubated and monitored in the neonatal intensive care unit. Although surgery was planned, the infant tragically passed away at 12 hours postpartum after initial stabilization.

DISCUSSION: About 60% of CDH cases are detected during routine fetal anatomical scans at 18 to 22 weeks. Definitive diagnosis involves visualizing abdominal organs in the fetal chest, often alongside polyhydramnios or hydrops. Findings vary based on whether the hernia is right or left-sided and the size of the defect.

CONCLUSION: CDH is a serious condition with morbidity rates of 40-50%. It may occur alone or with other congenital disorders. Newborns are at risk for pulmonary hypoplasia and hypertension, making early prenatal detection crucial for potential interventions.

Keywords: Congenital diaphragmatic hernia, CDH

Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia Ultrasound Findings

Fetal heart was displaced rightward due to a left-sided diaphragmatic hernia, with the stomach, intestines, and left lobe of the liver herniated into the thorax.

Polyhydramnios

The amniotic fluid index was evaluated as polyhydramnios based on the measurement of the deepest single pocket at 120 mm.

EP-49

Donnai Barrow Syndrome: A Rare Case Report

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INTRODUCTION: Donnai-Barrow syndrome (DBS) is a rare autosomal recessive disorder, characterized by distinctive craniofacial features, progressive vision and hearing loss, intellectual disability, agenesis of the corpus callosum (ACC), congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH), and omphalocele.

CASE: A 22-year-old pregnant woman, gravida 4, parity 3, was referred to our clinic at the 23rd week of gestation due to a diagnosis of corpus callosum agenesis in the fetus. The patient had a history of a consanguineous marriage (second-degree cousins). In the current pregnancy, ultrasonography revealed corpus callosum agenesis, hypertelorism (Figure 1), nasal bone hypoplasia, an abnormal facial profile, and diastematomyelia. The family opted for termination of the pregnancy. Whole exome sequencing (WES) analysis revealed a homozygous mutation in the LRP2 gene, consistent with a diagnosis of Donnai-Barrow syndrome (DBS). Clinical exome sequencing (CES) tests were conducted on the family, and both parents were found to be heterozygous carriers of the LRP2 gene mutation. In the postmortem examination, a female fetus with a body weight appropriate for the gestational age (23 weeks) was observed. The fetus exhibited midface hypoplasia, low-set ears, hypertelorism, a flat nasal bridge, and a short nose (Figure 2). Additionally, the right hand and fingers were positioned laterally (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION: This provided the family with the opportunity to pursue preimplantation genetic testing in future pregnancies for the pathogenic variant responsible for autosomal recessive Donnai-Barrow Syndrome. The case highlights the importance of whole exome sequencing (WES) in prenatal diagnosis, particularly in consanguineous marriages.

Keywords: LRP2 gene, Donnai-Barrow syndrome, WES

Figure 1

Ultrasound image of the fetus: Hypertelorism

Figure 2

Postmortem macroscopic image of the fetus: midface hypoplasia, low-set ears, hypertelorism, downslanting palpebral fissures, flattened nasal root

Figure 3

Postmortem macroscopic image of the fetus: right hand and fingers deviated laterally

EP-50

Early First-Trimester Diagnosis of Hypoplastic Left Heart Syndrome: A Case Report Highlighting Critical Diagnostic Pearls

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INTRODUCTION: This case report highlights the critical importance of first-trimester fetal echocardiography in the early diagnosis of hypoplastic left heart syndrome (HLHS).

CASE: A 29-year-old gravida 2 para 1 woman presented for routine first-trimester ultrasound examination. Fetal echocardiography revealed key findings consistent with HLHS, including a functional single ventricle, atretic mitral valve, small ascending aorta (1.4 mm), and reverse flow in the aortic arch. Additional findings included tricuspid regurgitation, restrictive foramen ovale, and an aberrant right subclavian artery. The combination of grayscale imaging, color Doppler, and meticulous evaluation of cardiac structures enabled an accurate diagnosis at this early gestational age. The patient was counseled regarding the poor prognosis associated with HLHS and offered termination, which she declined. Postnatally, the infant underwent balloon atrial septostomy and two subsequent surgical interventions but unfortunately succumbed at three months of age.

DISCUSSION: This case underscores the feasibility and significance of first-trimester diagnosis of major cardiac anomalies, particularly HLHS. Early detection allows for comprehensive counseling, informed decision-making, and appropriate perinatal management planning. Maternal-fetal medicine specialists and fetal cardiologists should be vigilant for specific ultrasonographic findings during first-trimester examinations.

CONCLUSION: This case emphasizes the need for a structured anatomical assessment protocol incorporating outflow tract views and color Doppler imaging to optimize detection rates of fetal cardiac pathology in the first trimester

Keywords: Hypoplastic left heart syndrome, first-trimester fetal echocardiography, congenital heart defects

Reverse flow in the Aortic arch and ARSA

Three vessel trachea view

Small Aorta with reverse flow

EP-51

The importance of differential diagnosis of cbc abnormalities in pregnancy and early puerperium: a case report

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Acute leukemia is infrequently diagnosed during pregnancy or puerperium, although the true incidence rate is unknown. In our presentation, we will explain the process and importance of AML diagnosis in a patient referred to our clinic with postpartum low hemoglobin and leukocytosis. G4P4Y4 34 year old patient referred to our hospital due to severe anemia at 2 hours postpartum. In the first hemogram evaluation, HGB: 5.5 (g/dL), PLT: 65 ($10^9/L$), WBC: 54.8 ($10^9/L$), so a peripheral blood smear was performed on the patient. The patient's only antenatal hospital application was in her 31st week of pregnancy. The patient, who had PLT: 87 ($10^9/L$), HGB: 8.5 gr/dL, WBC: 4.70 ($10^9/L$) in the hemogram evaluation, was referred to internal medicine for further examination, but the patient had not gone. Then the patient applied to the hospital at the time of delivery. In the postpartum peripheral blood smear evaluation, acute leukemia was considered firstly, the patient was transferred to the hematology department for detailed evaluation and follow-up. The final diagnosis was AML (with FTL3 mutation) and the patient was started on chemotherapy. In case of isolated thrombocytopenia or leukocyte abnormalities accompanying maternal anemia, it is important to make a meticulous differential diagnosis. The presence of malignant diseases such as acute leukemia among possible diagnoses increases the importance of differential diagnosis. As a result, in cases of isolated thrombocytopenia or leukocyte abnormalities accompanying maternal anemia, the patient should be evaluated with peripheral blood smear.

Keywords: Anemia, Leukocytosis, Puerperium

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Case Report: Prenatal Diagnosis Of DiGeorge Syndrome With Isolated Thymus Aplasia

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INTRODUCTION: DiGeorge Syndrome(DGS),associated with a 22q11.2 deletion,is the most common human microdeletion syndrome,occurring in approximately 1:4000 live births.It results from defective development of the third and fourth pharyngeal pouches.The classic presentation includes conotruncal cardiac anomalies,thymic hypoplasia,and hypocalcemia due to parathyroid hypoplasia.While most patients have sufficient thymic tissue for normal immune function,complete thymic aplasia,seen in a small percentage of cases,leads to severe immunodeficiency.

CASE: A 30-year-old Gravida 2 parity 1 woman at 23+6 weeks of gestation presented for a routine check-up.The triple test results were at low risk.Ultrasonography revealed fetal biometric measurements consistent with gestational age and mild unilateral ventriculomegaly (right 8 mm, left 11 mm).Doppler studies were standard.Due to the ventriculomegaly, the patient underwent amniocentesis.At 27 weeks, ultrasound showed a pregnancy consistent with gestational age,with an aplastic/hypoplastic thymus and ventricles were observed in normal range.Fetal echocardiography revealed no cardiac anomalies.Amniocentesis results showed a normal karyotype, but array CGH detected a 22q11.21 deletion, confirming DGS. The patient received genetic counseling and opted to continue the pregnancy.

CONCLUSION: This case highlights the significance of prenatal detection of DiGeorge Syndrome,particularly in the context of isolated thymic aplasia. Early identification through detailed ultrasonography and genetic testing, such as array CGH,allows for appropriate counseling and informed decision-making.While the absence of cardiac anomalies is notable, the risk of immune complications due to thymic aplasia underscores the importance of continued monitoring and postnatal management.The case emphasizes the value of genetic counseling in preparing families for potential challenges associated with DGS and optimizing outcomes for affected infants.

Keywords: DiGeorge Syndrome, Prenatal Diagnosis, Perinatology

Fetal cardiac four-chambers view at the 27th week of gestation

Thymic hypoplasia/aplasia at 27th week of gestation

Fetal face lateral view 27th week of gestation

Thymic Hypoplasia/Aplasia at 35th week of gestation

EP-53

Is mild discordance a sign of homopaternal superfecundation?

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A 35-year-old, G1 patient was admitted to the clinic. It was observed that the patient had a spontaneous dichorionic diamniotic twin pregnancy. From the first follow-up of the patient at 6 weeks and 3 days, it was determined that one fetus was larger than the other. This fetal weight difference continued until birth, but the discordance was always below 20%. When the patient's sexual history was questioned, it was learned that she had intercourse with the same person (partner) approximately every 1 week. The patient's water broke at the 35th week and was delivered via C/S. Fetal weights were female fetus 2100 and male fetus 2500 (16% discordance). Superfecundation is the fertilization of different ovaries by different sperm in the same cycle, and superfetation is the fertilization of different ovaries by different sperm in different cycles. It has been reported in the literature that some twins have slightly different gestational ages, so the heavier twin may have a larger gestational age, resulting in zygotes formed at different times (1). This type occurs through cases of superfecundation (formation of two zygotes from different matings). Superfecundation can only be proven in rare cases (those with two fathers). It is concluded that superfecundation by the same man is relatively common and therefore dizygotic twins often have different gestational ages. Superfecundation from different fathers is extremely rare due to the low probability of detection (2,3).

Keywords: superfecundation, twin pregnancy, discordance

Figure 1

First visit of the twins

Figure 2

Image of twins at 16 weeks

Figure 3

Neonatal discordance

Table 1

LMP	First fetus GA according to fetal USG(girl)	Second fetus GA according to fetal USG(boy)
11 w 6 d	11 w 2 d	12 w 2 d
16 w 3 d	16 w 2 d	17 w 3 d
20 w	20 w 1 d	21 w 1 d
24 w 3 d	24 w 3 d	25 w 2 d
29	31 w 2 d	32 w 3 d
33	33 w 2 d	34 w 1 d
35	35 w 1 d	36 w 2 d

Comparison of gestational age between fetuses according to ultrasonography USG: ultrasonography, LMP: Last menstrual period, GA: gestational age, w: week, d: day

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A Rare Case of Acute Abdomen in Pregnancy: Paratubal Cyst with Isolated Tubal Torsion

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INTRODUCTION: Acute abdomen in pregnancy is challenging due to symptom overlap with typical pregnancy symptoms. Conditions like ovarian torsion, cyst rupture, and appendicitis are among the common causes.

CASE: A 38-year-old nulligravida presented with a 12-hour history of persistent nausea, vomiting, and severe abdominal pain. She had no prior antenatal care. The patient was uncooperative and disoriented, displaying erratic behavior, such as screaming and attempting to throw herself off the gurney. Physical examination, and therefore diagnosis, was delayed due to her behavior. Her medical history included a gastric perforation as a complication of gastric banding.

DISCUSSION: Due to patient's lack of cooperation, the ultrasound examination was suboptimal but revealed a 14-week 3-day pregnancy with a live singleton fetus and a 134mm x 90mm hypoechoic cyst in the left adnexa. Given her history of gastric perforation and previous surgeries, laparotomy was chosen over laparoscopy to minimize any surgical risks. During the procedure, the cyst was found to be a paratubal cyst with isolated tubal torsion, closely mimicking ovarian torsion. Histopathological analysis confirmed the diagnosis after cystectomy.

CONCLUSION: This case demonstrates that paratubal cysts, although rare, can present as acute abdomen in pregnancy. Although the patient's surgical history impacted the decision-making process, laparoscopy is generally considered a safe and effective approach during pregnancy, with no significant differences in maternal or fetal outcomes.

She was discharged after 2 days and no complications occurred during her recovery period. Following a successful pregnancy, the patient delivered a healthy neonate at 37 weeks via vaginal delivery.

Keywords: Acute, torsion, pregnancy

Figure 1

Pelvic ultrasound examination paratubal cyst

Figure 2

Intraoperative image of the paratubal cyst

Figure 3

Histopathological image

EP-56

A Case Report: Noonan Syndrome

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The RASopathies are a group of autosomal dominant disorders with overlapping cardiac, growth, facial and neurodevelopmental features. Among these genetic syndromes, the most frequently reported is Noonan Syndrome (NS), a dysmorphic syndrome characterized after birth by hypertelorism, a downward eye slant, low-set posteriorly rotated ears (>80 percent), short stature (>70 percent), a webbed neck, cardiac anomalies, pulmonic stenosis (approximately 50 percent), deafness, motor delay, and a bleeding diathesis.

The prevalence of Noonan Syndrome is 1/1000-1/2500 live-borns. Noonan Syndrome is clinically heterogeneous and can present at any age.

Prenatal diagnosis: Fetuses with Noonan Syndrome may present with manifestations of disordered lymphatic development, which include increased nuchal translucency (most common), distended jugular lymphatic sacs/cystic hygroma, ascites, and generalized hydrops. Additional presenting features include renal anomalies such as hydronephrosis, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (20% of cases), congenital heart disease.

Noonan Syndrome shows significant genetic heterogeneity, which has led to 14 Noonan Syndrome forms being identified according to the type of inheritance (autosomal dominant vs recessive) and causal mutation. The most common causal mutation is a missense mutation in the PTPN11 gene on chromosome 12, 12q.24.1.

In this case, CVS was performed on the patient who was detected at high risk in the first trimester screening test and had bilateral jugular cysts, nuchal fold 7 mm, pleural effusion, pericardial effusion, hydrops fetalis, hypertelorism in the ultrasound. The rasopathy panel was studied in DNA. The c.1505C>T (p.Ser502Leu) variant was detected in the PTPN11 gene. With informed consent of the family, the pregnancy was terminated.

Keywords: Cystic hygroma, congenital anomaly, hydrops fetalis

1

Bilateral jugular cysts

2

Thick nuchal fold

3

Pleural effusion

4

Hypertelorism

5

6

EP-57

Dandy-Walker Malformation

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Dandy-Walker malformation (DWM) is the most common posterior fossa anomaly affecting cerebellar development, accounting for 1-4% of hydrocephalus cases. Diagnosis can be made through antenatal and postnatal ultrasound or CT and MRI at any stage. DWM is characterized by agenesis or hypoplasia of the vermis and cystic enlargement of the fourth ventricle, leading to elevation of the tentorium and torcular. It may present with anomalies such as neural tube defects. This case presents a newborn with hydrocephalus and cystic enlargement in the posterior fossa, delivered alive at 39 weeks.

The 39-year-old mother, G3P2, presented at 26 weeks for monitoring. Ultrasound showed FHR+ BPD-HC>97p, AC-11p, and FL<3p. The posterior fossa was enlarged, with a cisterna magna measuring 21 mm. The corpus callosum (CC) and cavum septi pellucid (CSP) were not visualized, and colpocephaly was noted in the lateral ventricles. The third ventricle was dilated and elevated. These observations suggested DWM and agenesis of the CC.

The patient gave birth at the 39th gestational week by vaginal delivery. The newborn did not require resuscitation and was admitted with spina bifida occulta. Cranial ultrasound indicated agenesis of the CC and a mega cisterna magna, consistent with DWM. A spinal MRI suggested tethered cord syndrome. The newborn was discharged with a follow-up recommendation at six months.

The prognosis of DWM is generally poor, with approximately 40% mortality, and most survivors have cognitive impairments. Treatment involves managing symptoms and comorbidities, and various surgical options are available.

Keywords: Dandy-Walker Malformation, Hydrocephalus, Cerebellar Dysfunction

Cranial MRI

Fetal MR

Fetal MR

Spinal MRI

Newborn

Ultrasound

Newborn

Ultrasound

Newborn

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Case Report on Large Omphalocele

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INTRODUCTION: Omphalocele is an anterior abdominal wall defect [1]. The incidence is 1 to 2 per 10,000 live births [2]. The size of the omphalocele sac can range from 2 to 10 cm, and 40-80% of these cases may have associated anomalies [3]. In this case, we discuss the prenatal diagnosis and management approach of omphalocele.

CASE: A 28-year-old patient was found to have a structure consistent with an omphalocele during the first trimester. CVS revealed a normal 46,XX karyotype. At 37 weeks, the omphalocele sac measured 85x72 mm, and the contents included intestines, liver, and gallbladder. A cesarean section was performed at 37 weeks and 5 days. On inspection, a large omphalocele sac was observed at the umbilical region. The newborn was operated on by pediatric surgery.

When omphalocele is detected antenatally, the defect and associated anomalies should be evaluated, and prenatal counseling should be provided to the family. If the family decides to continue the pregnancy, a multidisciplinary team, including obstetrics, pediatric surgery, and neonatology, should determine the optimal timing and mode of delivery, considering the size of the defect and the organs protruding outside the sac.

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Keywords: Large omphalocele, prenatal diagnosis

Ultrasound Image of Antenatal Omphalocele Sac

Subcutaneous Edema

Image of Omphalocele Sac After Birth

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